

VARIATION AND CONTINUITY IN MANTEÑO CERAMICS:
ISSUES OF SOCIAL/ETHNIC IDENTITY

BY

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SECTION I - INTRODUCTION

The Manteño culture (ca. A.D. 800-1532) encompasses some 700 years of Ecuadorian prehistory (Figure 1.1) and approximately 350km of Ecuadorian coastline (Figure 1.2). Dating to the Integration Period of the Ecuadorian prehistoric sequence constructed by Meggers (1966), the Manteño culture is the culmination of more than 9000 years of human presence in coastal Ecuador. Manteño is recognized archaeologically as a single material culture spread from north of the Bahía de Caraquez all the way south to the Gulf of Guayaquil, and including Isla Puná. It stretches inland to the hills of the Cordillera Colonche-Chongón and along the Santa Elena Peninsula into the Guayas Basin. As such, Manteño people lived in or exploited a variety of ecological zones, including the littoral of rocky cliffs and sandy beaches, mangroves, inland cloud forests, alluvial valleys, and the *bosque seco* closer to the coast.

Manteño culture arises out of what have been identified as the Guangala and Bahía cultures (ca. 500 B.C. – A.D. 800), two simple chiefdoms of the Regional Development Period, a period characterized by the proliferation of small, regional chiefdoms (Meggers 1966). The precise manner through which these cultures transformed and expanded into Manteño is still unknown. Evidence suggests that this was a change in scale rather than a change in kind (Mester 1990; Paulsen 1970).

Several distinctive material features differentiate Manteño from preceding groups, including extensive use of stone both for building materials and carved objects, and the polished black ceramics that have become the hallmark of the Manteño culture (Stothert 2001). In addition, Manteño is notable for its large urban settlements and complex settlement hierarchy. Within several large sites there is intra-site stratification with stone

foundation elite residences, stone foundation public buildings (some of these have in-situ stone seats) and earthen house mounds of the commoners. Manteño had a central position in a trade network stretching from West Mexico to southern Peru (Currie 1995; Norton 1986; Smith 1999).

Figure 1.1 – Abbreviated chronology of the coastal archaeological cultures.

Archaeological investigations of the Manteño culture have been conducted for approximately one hundred years, but many basic questions about the society are still unanswered, such as what social and political forms integrated the population over such a

large territory and how the society as a whole and in particular locations developed over time.

One of the most fundamental questions to be resolved is what was Manteño, in the sense of social or ethnic identity. Were all people using Manteño pottery – the most commonly used marker of identity among archaeologists – Manteño?. Based on ethnographic records, and the creativity of archaeologists, numerous names have been given to the material remains and people from different areas within the defined Manteño sphere of culture. Specifically, the terms “Manteño” or “Manteño del Norte” are used to refer to the remains in Manabí province, generally considered the heartland of the Manteño culture, while the terms “Huancavilca” or “Manteño del Sur” are used to refer to the remains in Guayas province (Estrada 1957a). Paulsen (1970) uses the term “Libertad” to refer to the remains in the same area. Manteño remains on Isla Puná, while less studied than those on the mainland, are generally referred to as the remains of the Punáe people (Zevallos 1995). Other authors use the term “Huancavilca” to refer to the entire corpus of material remains (Marcos 1995), preferring that term to “Manteño”. Finally, as a compromise, other authors retain the geographical boundaries but use the hyphenated term “Manteño-Huancavilca” (Holm 1982).

These sub-cultural distinctions rely mainly on delimiting geographical areas within the previously identified Manteño region and assigning regional labels. These practices are based primarily on reference to ethnohistoric documents, and can be rather impressionistic. Fewer authors have identified material correlates for these sub-traditions (see Estrada 1957a), and these material correlates may have more to do with local environmental context than with real cultural differences. For example, the restriction of

stone seats and stellae to the northern area of the Mañeno region is likely due to the limited availability of carvable limestone in other regions to the south (McEwan 2003). In the absence of limestone Manteño people in the south produced similar iconographic monuments using wood (Stothert and Cevallos 2001; Zevallos 1995).

Figure 2.2 – Geographical extent of Manteño culture (after Currie [2001:68]).

Missing from the definitions of regional sub-traditions is a systematic analysis of the material variation between these regions. This is a difficult task to accomplish given the scarcity of studies from which to build. However, as ceramic studies are the most complete data set for the Manteño culture, it is from that material that I will begin to address the actual variation within the Manteño territory.

This paper is motivated by two questions of very different scales. The first question seeks to assess the temporal and geographic variation within the Manteño ceramic assemblage, particularly as it relates to the divisions described above. I conduct this investigation (Section III) through an analysis and comparison of previous ceramic studies (Estrada 1957a, 1957b, 1962; Mester 1990; Paulsen 1970). Specifically, I am concerned with assessing if the socio-political divisions known through the ethnographic record (Section II) are reflected in the ceramic assemblage. For this reason I discuss the relationship between style and identity. In particular, I refer to fundamental work on ethnic groups and boundaries to develop a framework for identifying cultural groups in the past.

The second question I address evaluates the classification of ceramics from the site of Agua Blanca during my summer 2004 fieldwork there. I am concerned with assessing if the categories used for ceramic classification during the field season are valid and exclusive categories. I address this question through statistical analysis, primarily discriminant analysis (Section IV). Further, I examine how this ceramic assemblage compares to the previous studies presented in Section III. In particular, a comparison between what was recovered at Agua Blanca and the typologies proposed by other authors can point to the utility of their application at the site.

Thus, there are two broad theoretical concerns bound up in this dissertation. The first is a matter of culture history. There is a striking need to develop a chronology for the Manteño culture, not just to highlight the changes in the ceramic assemblage, but to understand how the culture changed and elaborated over time, how it developed out of the preceding small, regional chiefdoms into a complex entity that controlled most of coastal Ecuador. This paper is a step towards the development of a culture history of the area. By noting the temporal dimensions of the ceramic assemblage, as well as the geographic distribution of certain types of ceramics, a picture may begin to emerge of the spread of the Manteño styles across the region.

The second broad theme concerns the relationship between material culture and identity. This is by no means an uncomplicated relationship, and archaeologists have insisted in mapping strict cultural boundaries onto material remains as if this were an unambiguous act. By systematically addressing issues of temporal and geographic variation I lay the groundwork for a more nuanced approach to style in Manteño culture in future work.

SECTION II - MATERIAL CULTURE AND SOCIAL IDENTITY

The identification of social entities through patterning in material culture has formed the basis of archaeological investigations, particularly within the culture-history school (Trigger 1989). Here, stylistic variation was observed spatially and equated, primarily, with different culture groups in the past. The emphasis on geographically bounded material cultures has been linked to the need within the modern nation-state to identify and trace discrete ethnic groups from the past to the present in order to create a new national identity (Jones 1997; Shennan 1989).

This approach was critiqued by the New Archaeology (Binford 1962). In its place, artifacts were identified either as ‘technomic’, ‘socio-technic’, or ‘ideo-technic’. In this conception, style was viewed primarily as a by-product of other cultural processes, a largely non-functioning aspect of material culture that could be used to interpret cultural and ethnic identity (Jones 1997). Thus, though processual archaeologists criticized the culture-history approach to cultural difference, they largely retained its implications when examining ethnic groups.

In an important but little read article, George Kubler (1970) argues that the pace of change in a style varies by location, that “the metropolitan centers are fast, and the provincial margins are slow. The fast centers multiply as time goes on, while the slow margins diminish. The boundary between periods may occupy different centuries in different places” (Kubler 1970:129). Further, he argues that the traditional chronological schema (such as that employed in Figure 1.1) emphasizes the disconnects between stylistic phenomena, and suggests that these styles progress at the same rate in all locations. Thus, “the idea of style is best adapted to static situations, in cross-cut or

synchronous section. It is an idea unsuited to duration, which is dynamic, because of the changing nature of every class in duration” (Kubler 1970:140). Unfortunately, it is precisely this dynamic situation to which style is most often applied in the search for viewing the social development of the past. The implication of Kubler’s work is that stylistic chronologies need to be developed on a site-by-site basis and then compared regionally, rather than developing a regional chronology that is used to date sites based on stylistic elements.

Thus, while important critiques of the classificatory process have been offered, they have made little impact on how archaeologists conceive of style (Conkey 1990). Indeed, the most common use of style is for the investigation of social identity (Stark 1998). But we also need to look at stylistic variation as an indicator of change or continuity for cultural affiliation.

Isochrestic Variation and Emblematic Style

The investigation of style can be divided into roughly two theoretical camps; those who view style as a passive reflection of existing social groups and social boundaries, and those who view style as an active component in the creation and perpetuation of those same social groups and social boundaries. The conception of passive style views stylistic similarity as a reflection of social interaction between individuals or groups (Plog 1983). Thus, social interaction, such as ritual participation or trade, will result in stylistic similarities across cultural boundaries.

The conception of active style draws from the work of Wobst (1977), and argues that stylistic variation is used to communicate information about the maker or user. As

this view requires knowledge of symbols, and thus a certain level of shared cultural understanding, the utility of stylistic information diminishes over distance and thus variation in style can also serve to mark social boundaries.

The debate between these two views is best exemplified by the exchanges between Sackett (1977, 1985, 1990) and Weissner (1983, 1985, 1990). Sackett proposed isochrestic variation as indicators of group identity, while Weissner emphasized emblematic style for this same role.

Sackett (1977) starts with the compartmentalized view of style characteristic of the New Archaeology, but he argues that both style and otherwise “functional” aspects of material culture signal identity. Specifically, his concept of isochrestic variation emphasizes that the production of any material involves numerous steps, each of which offers the maker (or even the users) several different alternatives. The choices that an artisan makes are influenced by the tradition in which they learned and the culture in which they grew up Sackett (1985). In essence, artisans are guided by *habitus* (Bourdieu 1977), and variations in *habitus* reflect existing social boundaries. As isochrestic variation arises from deeply held, often unconscious structures, it is less susceptible to conscious manipulations, and therefore, Sackett (1990) holds that it is a better model of social affiliation than the emblematic model discussed below.

Wiessner provides the model of emblematic style (1983, 1985, 1990) in her advocacy of style as information exchange. Emblematic style is “formal variation in material culture that has a distinct referent and transmits a clear message to a defined target population about conscious affiliation or identity...Most frequently its referent will be a social group...and thus it will be used to express objective social attributes of

identity. Because it has a clear referent, emblematic style carries information about the existence of group boundaries and not about degree of interaction across or between them” (Wiessner 1983:257).

These studies focus on style as active or passive. They are underwritten by a desire to define groups in the archaeological record, and imply that this information is recoverable by archaeologists. They have provided the framework for subsequent scholars, who have both supported and challenged these conception of style and identity.

Newer investigations on the use of style for identifying social identity in the past have provided numerous cautionary tales, as well as highlighted alternative ways of accessing social identity in the past. In the next section I briefly outline the general directions provided by these studies. This information is presented within the context of relevant information concerning the Manteño that impact the ability of assessing cultural affiliation in the past, namely, the systems of trade that existed in ancient Ecuador, including the possible existence of a market economy, and the socio-political organization of the Manteño culture.

Style and Interaction – The Impact of Exchange on Stylistic Variation

Based on the normative concept of culture, many studies assume that homogeneity in material culture was a result of regular contact and interaction (Jones 1997; Plog 1983). Within the New Archaeology, specific focus was placed on stylistic elements, as style could not be “explained” through functional interpretations. Thus, social distance could be measured in terms of the similarities of material culture.

The role of trade has been demonstrated to have significant impact on the spatial patterning of stylistic elements. Dietler and Herbich (1998) in their examination of Luo ceramics, emphasize the role of the market in the distribution of different ceramic styles. They argue that understanding variation in material culture requires an understanding of the factors that condition the choices people make about style. They argue that Wobst (1977) and Wiessner's (1983) conception of style as an active communicator will be misleading and indeed misplaced in certain contexts, particularly when the contexts of consumption are ignored in favor of the context of production. From their study, it is apparent that the demands of the market result in a more varied ceramic assemblage, as well as impacting the spatial distribution of these remains. Thus, the conditions of consumption must be investigated in order to account for variation in ceramics assemblages. For this reason I turn now to the context of consumption within Manteño culture, namely the existence of long-distance trade as well as internal exchange.

Trade and Exchange in Manteño Society

The Manteño are perhaps best known for their role in a long distance oceanic trade system that extended from Peru to West Mexico (Zeidler 1977/78). Part of this renown derives from the fact that one of the earliest encounters between Spanish and the native inhabitants of the continent took place between the sailors of a Manteño balsa raft and a scouting Spanish ship commanded by Bartolome Ruiz, Francisco Pizarro's pilot. The account of this meeting is found in the *Relación de Samano-Xerez* (Samano-Xerez 1967 [1527-8]:67-8, as translated in McEwan 2003:98-9)

The route of these Manteño traders has been reconstructed to some extent. Records from West Mexico recount the regular appearance of people by boat from the south who would bring numerous goods to trade and occasionally spend five or six months in Mexico during bad weather (West 1961). Along with their textiles, semi-precious and precious stones, shell, and metal items, the Ecuadorians also introduced metallurgical techniques to Mexico (Hosler 1988; Paulsen 1974; Smith 1999). Mexican *Spondylus* shells were brought back to Ecuador. Some entered local exchange networks (Currie 1995) and some entered the exchange with Peru. This supply of *Spondylus* was augmented with shell from the Ecuadorian coast. In exchange for *Spondylus* shell, the Peruvians may have supplied the Ecuadorians with copper and semi-precious stones, including turquoise and lapis lazuli. (Alvarez 1999; Hosler et al. 1990; Marcos 2002). Figure 2.1 provides a distribution map of these trade routes.

Late prehispanic trade routes within ancient Ecuador have been described primarily for the northern and sierra regions. Salomon (1977/78, 1986, 1987) has argued for the existence of a hereditary group of professional merchants, the *mindaláes*. These merchants, though affiliated with a single chief or territory, operated across existing political boundaries, and served to bring important Amazonian or occidental resources to the polities of the sierra.

Embedded within his discussion of the *mindaláes* is evidence that at least some portion of ancient Ecuador operated on a market economy. Although these traders would have been the primary means of transporting goods into different ecological and political areas, a quasi-standardized currency facilitated the exchange of a variety of goods. This currency occurred in two forms, the first being strands of shell beads, called *chaquirá*

Trade routes within the Manteño region have not been well examined. It is likely that each settlement was specialized to some degree, at least in terms of subsistence production (Stothert 2001), and that trade transported regional specialties, such as tar from the Santa Elena Peninsula, to other areas of the Manteño region. Silva (1984) has suggested a symbiotic relationship between coastal villages, specializing in fishing and marine resources, and inland valley villages, who specialized in agricultural production. Both types of settlements were generally contained within a single chiefdom, allowing for the easy flow of comestibles between settlements.

Although the exact nature of trade in the Manteño and larger Ecuadorian regions is still unknown, it is clear that such interaction did exist. According to the models presented above, this extensive interaction is likely to have resulted in a level of homogenization in the spatial patterning of at least some material remains. Ceramic vessels in particular, as containers for different comestibles and other exchange goods, may be particularly susceptible to the homogenizing distribution of trade. Thus, there is an expectation that, due to trade networks, material culture should be relatively homogenous across the different Manteño regions discussed in the introduction.

Style and Ethnicity – The Impact of Sub-Group Identity on Stylistic Variation

Beginning with the New Archaeology, archaeological investigations of ethnicity have sought out stylistic elements for information concerning the boundaries of groups of people. These investigations essentially retained the same problematic concept of culture, which they themselves had criticized, but focused on the smaller ethnic group rather than the larger cultural group (Jones 1997).

This view was gradually replaced with a more dynamic conceptualization of ethnicity as an aspect of social organization that “involves the active maintenance of cultural boundaries in the process of social interaction, rather than a passive reflection of cultural norms” (Jones 1997:28).

Of principal importance for these new investigations of ethnicity was the work of Fredrik Barth in his edited volume, *Ethnic Groups and Social Boundaries* (1969). His introduction to the volume emphasized creation and maintenance of ethnic boundaries, involving the conscious deployment of pertinent symbols to create a we/they distinction. For Barth, this self-ascription and recognition by others must be central to any understanding of ethnic groups, particularly as ethnic groups persist despite inter-ethnic interaction and reciprocal interdependence (Barth 1969).

Barth’s position has been criticized as focusing on the interaction between groups at the expense of the cultural context within which they are situated (Jones 1997; Stone 2003). An alternative has been offered by Bentley (1987), who focuses on the content of the cultural systems through an analysis of *habitus*. Bentley conceives of ethnicity as a largely unconscious participation in preexisting structures.

Although Barth and Bentley disagree about how ethnicity is created and maintained, they both agree that ethnic affiliation results in group differences. From an archaeological perspective, then, ethnic affiliation should result in differences in material culture, whether that be in the symbols and designs deployed on different medium, or in the habitual creation and use of different types of material culture.

Sub-Group Identity in Manteño Society

Several regional sub-traditions have been proposed for the coast of Ecuador, all subsumed under the heading of Manteño. These regional subtraditions are based on a combination of ethnohistoric information, limited archaeological evidence, and the political currency of archaeology in the present. Thus, while an almost identical material culture characterizes the entire coast of Ecuador, three terms are often used to refer to the people in three different regions; “Manteño” or “Manteño del Norte” to indicate the remains spreading from Manabí province to the north of Guayas province, “Huancavilca” or “Manteño del Sur” to indicate the people who lived on the Santa Elena Peninsula and in the Guayas Basin, and “Punáe” to refer to the people who occupied Isla Puná in the Gulf of Guayaquil (Figure 2.2). In this section I present a brief discussion of these regional divisions (for a full discussion of the shifting boundaries and terminology see Stothert 2001).

Much of the information we have about Manteño social organization, including these sub-traditions, is derived from the ethnohistorical record. Jijón y Caamaño (1941), in a discussion on the ethnic composition of prehispanic coastal Ecuador, was the first to outline the tripartite division of the coastal Manteño culture, based on the written accounts of the Spanish and other early explorers. He divided this larger territory into those of the *Manabita*, encompassing the northern zone, the *Guancavilca*, concentrated around the city of Guayaquil and on the Santa Elena Peninsula, and the *Puneña*, located on Isla Puná. Though these groups spoke a variety of mutually unintelligible languages, they were united in a confederation of merchants that operated up and down the Pacific coast.

Geographical territories of ■ Manteño del Norte ■ Guancavilca ■ Punáes

Figure 2.2 – Approximate boundaries of the Manteño del Norte, Huancavilca, and Punáes

Subsequent scholars expanded on this original division, providing more details about the political organization in each area. Most is known ethnohistorically about the Punáes (Punaña in Jijón y Caamaño’s works). This is due to the extended stay of the Spanish on the island, and the subsequent “betrayal” of the Spanish at the hands of the

Punáes (Cieza de León 1973 [1553]). These records speak of seven chiefs on the island who were ruled over by a supreme chief, Tomalá (Volland 1995). The island was a hub for marine trade, and some scholars have proposed that it was the center of a Huancavilca (Guancavilca in the writings of Jijón y Caamaño) united polity (Zevallos 1995) that controlled lands on the Santa Elena Peninsula, in the mouth of the Guayas river, and in present day El Oro province. Outside the geographic boundary of the island, however, this geographic projection is open to interpretation. Despite this centralized, quasi-autonomous, political organization on the island, the archaeological materials that have been recovered clearly fall within the Manteño tradition (Stothert 2001).

Of the three groups outlined above, the Huancavilca area and people have been least clearly defined in the literature. The Huancavilca area, in particular the Santa Elena Peninsula, has been portrayed as a sort of Manteño backwater (Bushnell 1951). Sites tend to be smaller than those in the northern region, and there is an observed trend of village fissioning after the previous Guangala phase (Masucci 1998). Only one ceremonial-political center has been discovered thus far, the site of Loma de Los Cangrejitos (Marcos 1981), compared to the numerous centers in the north.

Despite the paucity of discovered remains in the south, authors have proposed a Huancavilca state that encompassed the area presently recognized as that of the Manteño culture (Marcos 1995; Zevallos 1995). In these models, a central political authority, located on Isla Puná (Zevallos 1995) or the land around Salangome (Marcos 1995), is seen to control land south towards Tumbes and north into the Esmeraldas Province. While these hypotheses explain the widespread distribution of a single material culture,

they ignore compelling information, particularly from the northern area, of localized political control.

Based on ethnohistoric documents (Benzoni 1967[1550]; Cieza de León 1973[1553]; Sámano-Xerez 1937[1528] in McEwan 2003; Torres de Mendoza 1868[1548] in Silva 1984; Zarate 1965[1555]) and confirmed by archaeology, it is known that the Manteño del Norte were composed of five chiefdoms, *señoríos*, spanning from the Bahía de Caraquez to northern Guayas province. The same *Relación* that describes Manteño long distance trade also provides several place names, some of which can be recognized even today, and gives a glimpse at the socio-political organization that existed in the northern region at that time:

Those three Indians that I mentioned who were captured on the vessel and taken to the captains quickly learned our language. *It seems that they were from a land and people known as Salangome...*the people in that land are of better quality and bearing than Indians because they are of better appearance and color and very intelligent and they have a language like Arabic and evidently they rule over the Indians that I mentioned from Tacamez and of the Bay of San Mateo and of Nancabez and of Tovirisimi and Conilope and Papagayos and Tolona and Quismos and Coaque and Tonconjes and Aranypaxaos and Pintagua and Caralobes, Xamaxejos, Came and Amotopce, Docoa, all towns of the lowlands that have been discovered along the coast and of all that other part of the coast in the polity of Salangome where there were four towns together under the rule of one Lord which are the said Salangome and Tusco and Seracapez and Salango where there are many sheep and pigs and cats and dogs and other animals and ducks and doves and there they make the tunics that I mentioned above of wool and cotton and craft beads and pieces of silver and gold and they are a cultured people so it appears having many tools of copper and other metals with which they work their tools and extract gold and practice all forms of agriculture and have towns with well planned streets and they have many different kinds of crops and much order and justice among themselves and the women are very white and well dressed and the great majority of them are craft workers. (Samano-Xerez 1967 [1527-8]:67-8, as translated in McEwan 2003, emphasis mine).

Embedded in this passage is a suggestion that the inhabitants in these towns, and presumably the smaller villages and hamlets subsumed within it, identified themselves as a distinct group separate from those around them; they identified themselves as Salangomeños, or the people of Salangome. From the preceding discussion of ethnicity, it is apparent that one condition for the identification of an ethnicity has been met: that a we/them conceptualization of interaction was a pertinent division in society.

The famed balsa raft originated from the town of Salango, one of four towns under the rule of the Lord of Salangome in the town of the same name. From the place names included here, it appears that the Lord of Salangome exerted control over the coastal towns of the area, including those belonging to other *señoríos*. Norton (1986) has suggested that the League of Merchants hypothesized by Jijón y Caamaño (1941) was thus centered within this polity.

The towns of this *Señorío de Salangome* (Salangome, Tusco, Sercapez, and Salango) have been identified as the modern towns of Agua Blanca, Machalilla, Puerto Lopez, and Salango, respectively (McEwan 2003; Silva 1984), all located within the modern Manabí province of coastal Ecuador.

Three other *señoríos* have been identified in the Manteño del Norte region, the *Señoríos* of Jocay, Picoaza, and Charapotó. These *Señoríos* have been identified with specific ancient, and occasionally, modern towns (Figure 2.3). The *Señorío de Jocay* was composed of the towns of Jocay, Jaramijo, Camilloa, and Cama. Once again, the principal town of this *Señorío* was Jocay, which has been identified as the modern town of Manta. The *Señorío de Picoaza* was composed of the towns of Picoaza, Tohalla,

Misbay, and Solongo (McEwan 2003; Silva 1984). The *Señorío de Charapotó* was located near the Bahía de Caraquez, at the site known as Japotó (Sánchez et al. 2003).

A single *señorío* was identified in ethnohistories for the Huancavilca region, that of Colonche (Benzoni 1967[1550]). It was situated at the modern town of Colonche, and includes the archaeological remains from La Libertad (Stothert 2001). Other *señoríos* were likely located near the modern settlements of Chongon and Chanduy (ibid).

Figure 2.3 – Map depicting the location and approximate territory of the three central *Señoríos* (McEwan 2003:129).

If each of these *Señoríos* was conceived of as distinct entities, as the passage suggests, it may be more accurate to speak of Salangomeños, Jocaños, Picozaños, Charapoteños, and Coloncheños, than of Manteños or even Manteños del Norte. The

information presented here highlights the difference between archaeological cultures and living cultural affiliation, and further complicates attempts to illuminate the differences that may have existed in the past. Clearly, the people living in the past recognized a more nuanced group affiliation than we have identified or constructed through the archaeological remains.

Ethnicity, at its core, is simply another kind of specialized group identity (Shennan 1989; Stone 2003). Therefore, it may be useful to think about the requirements and characteristics of ethnic identity when attempting to identify social groups in the past, particularly when ethnohistoric documents exist to aid in the process. At its core, the investigation of ethnicity, whether in the past or in the present, attempts an emic conceptualization of social groups, a conceptualization very much at odds with the etic definition of archaeological cultures.

From the discussion above it is clear that tantalizing information exists to suggest the presence of regionally conceived identities, if not ethnicities, within the broader Manteño region. From the models presented above, the presence of these ethnicities or regional identities, and the importance of boundary maintenance for ethnic identities, should result in the regionally demarcated distribution of material remains.

Summary

From the preceding discussion, it is clear that, for the Manteño case, there are conflicting expectations for the patterning of the material culture. The presence of extensive trade would serve to homogenize the material assemblage, or to carry identity-marking materials outside of the associated territory. The existence of regional

ethnicities, on the other hand, could have generated the spatial segregation of material remains. In the following section I examine the ceramic studies of previous authors in order to identify which of the preceding models most accurately describes the Manteño ceramic materials.

Essentially, I am asking if considerations of regional identity, on the one hand, or mutual intelligibility in situations of trade, on the other, impacted the production of Manteño ceramics. While an all-or-nothing expectation is unrealistic, a homogenous assemblage would indicate the importance of trade and contact, while geographically delimited ceramic variation would indicate the primacy of regional identity.

SECTION III - PREVIOUS CERAMIC STUDIES

Although studies of Manteño ceramics span almost half a century we still lack a master sequence to differentiate the more than seven hundred years of Manteño occupation. In this section I present the previous Manteño ceramic studies. These studies include both single site and multi site studies from across the Manteño region. This literature review describes the ceramic types identified by each author, as well as any geographic or temporal variation identified by the authors.

Emilio Estrada

Emilio Estrada's studies (1957a, 1957b, 1962) of Ecuadorian ceramics provide an excellent data set upon which to build, both of Manteño ceramics and those from previous cultures. A particular strength of his work is that he draws on materials from stratigraphic excavations at numerous sites on the coast of Ecuador, notwithstanding his excavations by ten centimeter arbitrary levels (see Paulsen 1970). He endeavored to condense this broad range of data into several discrete types. Further, his numerous seriations attempt to highlight the temporal dimensions of these types.

Estrada's principal weakness stems from his focus on paste in defining ceramic types. This creates two problems. First, it subsumes numerous rim shapes, and thus vessel forms, under a single paste type. This obscures the variation that existed in the Manteño ceramic assemblage, a variation that Estrada himself recorded in his sherd counts (Figure 3.1). Second, this emphasis on paste types could serve to create artificial differences that did not exist to the Manteño population. Specifically, if peoples, though united in a single regional identity, used clays and tempering materials that were locally

Ordinario and *Manabitas* types appear fairly consistently throughout the Manteño period, and are apparently a continuation of a paste type present in the Guangala period as well.

Second is *Manteño Pulido* (Estrada 1957a:72, 1957b:38), a polished ware made of light brown, black, or red clay and tempered with fine grains of sand. This paste type was used for a variety of fine-ware vessels, including *ollas globulares* and *compoteras*. It also appears with relatively consistent frequency throughout the Manteño period.

There are several other polished types as well. These include *Chanduy Pulido* (Estrada 1957a:73, 1957b:39, 1962:44), named after a town on the coast of the Santa Elena Peninsula, made of red clay and tempered with medium grains of sand, a type which exists in the earlier Chirije phase and diminishes through time.

Playas Gris Pulida (Estrada 1957a:72, 1957b:38, 1962:50), named after the town of Playas in southern Ecuador, consists of a grey clay mixed with kaolin that appears almost black after firing. This paste type was used for *ollas* and *compoteras*, and occasionally had parallel or circular lines painted onto the polished surface. This type was prevalent throughout the Manteño period, but is most prevalent in the Chirije phase.

Puná Pulido (Estrada 1957a:74), named for Isla Puná in the Gulf of Guayaquil, is very similar the *Playas Gris Pulida* type, with the exception that it primarily consists of red clays. It occurs primarily on the island, but Estrada gives no description of its temporal characteristics.

The *Manteño Rojo Pulido Fino* (Estrada 1957b:42) type is made out of red clay and tempered with fine sand. It is used for *ollas* and *tazas*, and is a continuation of a similar Guangala type. Estrada provides no further information as to the temporal or geographic extent of this type.

Finally, the *Manteño Gris Pulido* (Estrada 1962:47) type is composed of grey clay tempered with fine grains of sand or kaolin that appears dark grey or black when fired. This type is used for *ollas*, *tazas*, and *compoteras*. It is present throughout the Chirije and Manteño phases.

These *pulido* types are often transformed through a variety of decorative measures into new types that Estrada identified. The *Manteño Bruñido* (Estrada 1957a:72, 1957b:38, 1962:46) type is closely allied to *Pulido* wares, as it consists of *Manteño Pulido* wares that have had lines burnished onto the vessel. This frequently occurs on *compotera* forms. While Estrada's seriations are at times ambiguous, it appears that *Manteño Bruñido* is more frequent in the later portions of the Manteño period.

The *Manteña Modelada* (Estrada 1957a:74, 1957b:40) type consists of vessels that have human or animal faces molded onto vessels of the *Manteña Pulida* type, often occurring with sections of burnished designs. These *mascarones* are added to *olla* forms, as well as to *compoteras*. Estrada does not describe the temporal or geographic range of this type.

The last transformation of the *Pulido* type that Estrada identifies is the *Manteño Negativo* type (Estrada 1957b:42), in which bands of negative resist paint are added on top of the *Pulido* type. This negative paint technique is often used for *compoteras*.

A common decorative technique is that of incised and excised designs. These are generally applied to polished finewares, and consist of geometric designs or stylized pelicans. Estrada identifies three types, *Manteño Inciso Exciso*, *Manteño Gris Fino Inciso*, and *Manteño Inciso y Pulido*. The *Manteño Inciso Exciso* (Estrada 1957a:73,

1957b:39, 1962:48) type consists of light brown clay tempered with very fine grains of sand and highly polished. This paste is commonly found on *ollas*, *compoteras*, and *tazas*.

The *Manteño Gris Fino Inciso* (Estrada 1957b:41) consists of grey clay tempered with fine sand, polished and incised with a variety of designs. This type occurs on *taza* and *compotera* forms, and exists from the Guangala through Manteño phases. Estrada provides no additional information about the temporal dimensions of this type.

The *Manteño Inciso y Pulido* (Estrada 1957a:73, 1957b:39, 1962:48) type consists of dark grey, almost black, clay tempered with very fine sand. It is highly polished as well, and found on *compoteras* and *tazas*. Estrada suggests that designs in the south are more rectangular while those in the north are more curvilinear. Both types are rare in the ceramic assemblage but are present throughout the Manteño period.

The *Playas Gris Grabado* (Estrada 1957b:39, 1962:49), or simply *Playas Grabado* (Estrada 1957a:72), type consists of engraved designs. While the incised and excised designs are performed on wet clay, the engraved designs on *Playas Gris Grabado* are added to the vessel when it is greenware or after it has been fired. Generally this type consists of a highly polished grey or dark brown clay tempered with kaolin or very fine sand. Vessel forms include several *olla* shapes as well as *compoteras*. This type occurs infrequently but regularly throughout the Manteño period. Estrada suggests that this form is most common near the southern town of Playas and may have originated there.

An additional type, *Manteño Grabado sobre Rojo Pulido* (Estrada 1957b:42), consists of a highly polished red clay tempered with very fine sand. It is primarily found on *olla* forms, and seems to be restricted to Manabí province. Estrada provides no information as to its temporal distribution.

The *Chanduy Rojo en Bandas* (Estrada 1957a) type consists of a reddish clay used for utilitarian vessels, including *ollas* and plates. These types have a band of red paint applied with a finger around the rim of the vessel. These types appear at the beginning of the Manteño phase. While this type is named after the town on the Santa Elena Peninsula, Estrada does not describe the geographic distribution of this type.

There are several additional, minor types that Estrada (1957b) identifies, most without any indication of their temporal or geographic distribution. These include *Manteño Rojo Lavado* (Estrada 1957b:41), a red clay used for utilitarian wares with a thin wash of red paint, and *Manteño Blanco sobre Ordinario* (Estrada 1957b:43), in which a white wash of paint is applied over *Manteño Ordinario*. Finally, the *Manteño o Guayas Rojo Pintado* (Estrada 1957b:41), type consists of red clay tempered with sand and painted with a thick layer of red paint. This type is limited to Guayas province but exists in various cultures preceding and including Manteño.

Although, with very few exceptions, such as the *Rallador Manabita*, there is little geographic variation within the ceramic assemblage, Estrada does distinguish a “Manteño del Sur” or “Huancavilca” group from the “Manteño del Norte,” or simply “Manteño” group. These are both distinct from the “Punáes” on Isla Puná (1957a). Although the ceramic assemblage is thus largely undifferentiated, Estrada (1962:86) does provide several points at which the two geographic regions diverge (Table 3.1), such as the presence of stone sculptures in the north, and the absence of urn burials in that region as well. In my personal experience however, urn burials are indeed present in the north. Further, the absence of stone sculptures in the south may be due to the fact that limestone deposit are absent in the south (McEwan 2003). Thus, it is not simply a presence-

Elementos Culturales	Manteños del Norte	Manteños del Sur
Casas con cimientos de piedra	Si	No
Terrazas agricolas	Si	No
Entierro secundario en urnas funerarias dobles*	No	Si
Supulcros de pozo*	Si	No
Estatuas de piedra	Si	Pocas
Sillas de piedra	Si	No
Estelas de piedra	Si	No
Rompacabezas estrellas de piedra	Si	No
Rallador Manabita	Si	No
Manteño Pulido	Si	Si
Manteño Bruñido	Si	Si
Manteño Inciso y Pulido, lineas rectas	Si	Si
Manteño Inciso y Pulido, volutes	Si	No
Manteño Inciso y Exciso	Poca	Si
Milagro Peinado (comercio)	Si	No
Decoración pelicano	Si	Si
Decoración felino	Si	Si
Decoración serpentioforme	Si	Si
Figurillas moldeadas Manteñas	Si	Pocas
Torteros abundantes*	Si	No
Metalurgia abundantes	Poco	Si

Table 3.1 – Differences between northern and southern regions of Manteño culture, after Estrada (1962:86). Those differences pertaining to ceramics are shaded grey.

*These conclusions have been invalidated by subsequent work.

absence of certain materials recorded in Estrada’s chart that distinguishes these two regions, if in fact they can be distinguished at all on the basis of recoverable material culture.

As stated in the introduction to this section, Estrada’s emphasis on paste type serves to both obscure and create variation within the ceramic assemblage. His emphasis on paste types places clay color and decoration at the forefront of his analysis. Although some of the types he outlines appear to have a limited distribution within a certain region, it is possible, as these types crosscut a number of forms, that what these types truly record is differences in locally available material rather than differences in actual vessel types. Further, while some of the paste types he identified are used for utilitarian wares, the majority of them represent fine wares. Thus, his analysis is skewed towards the materials

types are in large part a continuation of those found in earlier cultures on the coast. Unfortunately this means that there are no recognizable ceramic types that can be used as sensitive temporal indicators in the course of excavations. Additionally, those types that are restricted to the Manteño period appear to spring up suddenly and persist unchanged throughout the Manteño period. Therefore, although Estrada's type-variety method has fulfilled its purpose in the initial identification and description of the ceramic assemblage, it holds limited utility in further ceramic studies.

Alison Paulsen

Allison Paulsen's (1970) analysis is focused on creating a ceramic sequence for the Santa Elena Peninsula. She used surface collections to conduct a similarity seriation and then verified this seriation with stratigraphic excavations following natural levels. These excavations also allowed her to tie in her ceramic seriation with absolute dates based on radiocarbon samples taken from three of her four identified phases.

Her analysis focuses on the Libertad (Manteño) phase and the preceding Guangala phase. She argues that the Libertad ceramics are not a continuation of the previous Guangala ceramics (Paulsen 1970:139). Her radiocarbon dates suggest a two hundred year absence of human population on the Santa Elena Peninsula, which she relates to a period of severe drought (Paulsen 1970:17). Thus the break between Guangala and Libertad ceramics at this local level may simply be due to human migration. Ann Mester's research (1990), discussed below, is able to fill in these missing two hundred years and provide a more gradual picture of ceramic change.

Paulsen identifies six Libertad phases which she divides into two major sections, called Early and Late. The Early phase consists of Libertad 1 and Libertad 2. Libertad 1, dating to 1000 A.D. \pm 80 (Paulsen 1970:58), is characterized by bell rim jars, a criss-cross or “laddered” burnished design on the body of these jars, as well as several types of shallow plates and several types of bowls. Libertad 2, a phase without any stratigraphic evidence, is characterized by bell rim jars, pedestal plates, and polished black bowls. It was defined on stylistic grounds as an intermediary between Phase 1 and later phases.

The Late phase consists of Libertad Phases 3 through 6. Libertad 3, also without stratigraphic evidence, is characterized by bell rim jars, engraved decorations, and pattern burnishing. It was defined on stylistic grounds as an intermediary between Phases 2 and 4. Libertad 4, dating to 1350 A.D. \pm 100 (Paulsen 1970:58), is characterized by engraved designs, black bowls, and pedestal plates with resist motifs. This phase is of extremely short duration, as are the following phases.

Libertad 5, dating to 1400 A.D. \pm 100 (Paulsen 1970:58), is characterized by excised designs of zoomorphic and anthropomorphic figures on bell-rim jars, as well as by incised black polished bowls. The final phase, Libertad 6, lacks stratigraphic evidence. It is characterized by the same zoomorphic and anthropomorphic figures, this time excised on pedestal plates.

In summary, Early Libertad ceramics are differentiated from Late Libertad ceramics primarily by the absence of incised or excised designs. Early Libertad, phases 1 and 2, encompass a larger period of time, suggesting more gradual stylistic change. Late Libertad, phases 3 through 6, are characterized by relatively rapid changes in stylistic elements.

The benefit of Paulsen's analysis lies in its linkages between ceramic seriation and absolute dating. Unfortunately, her analysis is focused almost exclusively on fine wares, which limits the investigation of ceramic change to those vessels that would have been used by elite individuals. The only mention she makes of utilitarian wares concerns "the large coarse water jars [which] are found in every Libertad phase" (Paulsen 1970:154), though there is a decrease in rim width over time.

Although her analysis only examines ceramics from the Santa Elena Peninsula, Paulsen does speak to the wider geographic applicability of her study (Paulsen 1970:137). She takes issue with Estrada's nomenclature concerning the Manteño. As he presents it (Estrada 1957b), "Manteño" proper refers to the area around Manta, from where it derives its name. Estrada refers to the remains from the Santa Elena Peninsula as "Manteño del Sur," and aligns this area with the "Huancavilca". Paulsen argues that as the Huancavilca were living in the Guyas Basin at the time of Spanish conquest and the Peninsula was uninhabited at that time, Huancavilca is an inappropriate term to use for the prehistoric remains on the Peninsula. Instead, she offers the term "Libertad" to account for the remains of the Santa Elena Peninsula. However, this argument for the uniqueness of the southern material culture is undermined when she states, in reference to a ceramic assemblage from Cerro de Hojas, near Manta, that "although this pottery is from a region far and entirely distinct from the Santa Elena Peninsula, it contained so many of the Libertad 1 markers that one would unhesitatingly assign it to that phase" (Paulsen 1970:144). Thus, at least in this early phase of Libertad materials, the affinity between the ceramic assemblages in the northern and southern extents are virtually identical.

Mester Ceramic Analysis

Ann Mester's (1990) ceramic analysis comprises the most detailed analysis of Manteño ceramics to date, specifically the early period of Manteño occupation (the latest radiocarbon date is around 1300 A.D. [Mester 1990:531]). Her analysis is derived from stratigraphic excavations, providing a secure context for each classified form. Most importantly, Mester's analysis includes a detailed examination of both utilitarian and fine wares, and provides extensive documentation and illustration of each vessel type that she identified. This allows for future investigations to build directly off of her work. A further value of her work is that it addresses the period of time that Paulsen (1970) had to ignore due to depopulation on the Santa Elena peninsula.

Mester conducted her dissertation research in the late 1980s at Los Frailes, a site located on the outskirts of the modern town of Machalilla. As part of this research she excavated a 2x2 m cut into a midden located on the northern edge of the central plaza. The cut was excavated down to sterile soil, at a depth of two meters. From this she recovered a diagnostic sample of 964 diagnostic sherds.

She first grouped sherds according to variations in rim and lip shape. She found that differences in paste and temper mapped directly onto differences in vessel form, distinguishing two classes of vessels, coarse utilitarian wares and finer serving wares. This distinction corresponds to variation in paste, vessel form, and vessel decoration (Mester 1990:95). She identified 778 vessel attributes in her sample, which she was able to assign to nine vessel types.

Coarse or utilitarian wares are characterized by red clays with natural inclusions of mica, pyrite and grit, and are often tempered with volcanic rock. This type of clay occurs naturally in the area, specifically near Puerto Lopez and the Buenavista drainage west of Agua Blanca (Mester 1990:96). She identifies six vessel types within the category of utilitarian wares: “1) independent restricted globular pots with strongly everted rims (*ollas*); 2) simple restricted globular pots (*neckless ollas*); 3) independent unrestricted cylindrical pots with everted rims (*jars*); 4) dependent restricted necked jars with everted rims (*necked jars*); 5) shallow plates with simple rims bearing red paint; and 6) large flat-bottomed plates with marked rims and interiors with finger-dragging designs (called *ralladores* by Estrada, 1957a, and Paulsen, 1970)” (Mester 1990:95).

Fine wares are characterized by fine sandy tan clays with clear and black mica, pyrite, graphite, iron nodules, and white or dark fine grit as natural inclusions. These clays are often used without temper, but occasionally possess sherd or crushed rock temper. This clay is present in the area around the site of Los Frailes where she conducted her excavations (Mester 1990:97). She identifies three vessel types within the category of fine wares: “1) Shallow plates supported on tall annular pedestals with variable rim treatment (*pedestal plates*); 2) Jars with constricted necks and widely flaring rims, globular, inflected or carinated bodies, and supported on round, flat, or short flaring pedestal bases (*bell rim jars*). Necks can be short with a high shoulder, or very long, forming a graceful bottle form. Bell rims and flaring pedestal bases are also found on anthropomorphic and zoomorphic effigy jars of the same paste and bearing the same surface treatment; 3) A wide variety of bowl forms, including simple *hemispherical bowls* with direct rims, slightly *restricted bowls* with incurving rims with slight interior

thickening, *flaring walled bowls*, and *carinated bowls* with direct rims” (Mester 1990:96).

From the fifteen stratigraphic contexts recovered in her excavation she was able to identify four ceramic phases (A-D) based on significant breaks in the physical stratigraphy (Mester 1990:123). Several vessel forms are highly sensitive temporal markers. Olla forms in particular vary over time (Mester 1990:100), as Phase A is characterized by many more olla forms than later phases, including a red-slipped rim ollas that is limited to Phase A. The coarse jar form and a variety of bowl forms in mirror these general trends in olla forms. On the other hand, *ralladores* and pedestal plates appear to be consistent throughout the four phase.

Generally, Mester (1990:123) notes an increase in standardization over time (Figure 3.3). Phase A is characterized by a proliferation of vessel forms, particularly in ollas, coarse jars, and bowls. She suggests that “while the coarse ware appears to be the result of a well-maintained and standardized ceramic tradition, the bowls are clearly a collection of forms of disparate origins,” representing a continuation from Guangala or Bahía forms (Mester 1990:123). This is unsurprising due to the conservative behavior of utilitarian forms, but may also point to the importance of bowl forms in rituals of community solidarity in the preceding phases (see Rowe 2003).

Within Mester’s sample, as it progresses to what she calls “Early Manteño” (Mester 1990:124), there is an increasing standardization of vessel forms, both of utilitarian and of fine wares. Standardization in vessel forms and designs has been linked to increasing complexity of social organization, though not unproblematically. Often, three reasons are given for the increasing standardization of ceramics (Arnold 2000;

Blackman et al. 1993; Costin 1991; Rice 1981, 1991). First, standardization is seen to increase with specialized production, as potters begin to produce vessels for exchange

Figure 3.3 – Phases A through D from Los Frailes, showing decreasing variability in ceramic forms through time (Mester 1990:363-6).

outside of the household. Second, increased routinization of production will lead to greater skill and greater standardization. Finally, production may become more standardized as elites take control of production or access to resources. As such, craft specialization is often correlated with increased socio-political complexity (Peregrine 1991). As these ceramics are found within the context of a specialized workshop, I think it likely that ceramic standardization increased as social complexity increased.

Specifically, ceramic forms decreased in number as society evolved from the simpler chiefdoms of the Guangala and Bahía cultures to the more complex Manteño chiefdom.

To address the applicability of her analysis to the broader geographic region, Mester compares her analysis to that of Paulsen (1970). She states that the Libertad ceramics identified by Paulsen “differed from the Los Frailes material only in that the Libertad source clay is coarser and less uniform than the finer clay used for the Los Frailes pots. [They] clearly fall within a single ceramic tradition, whose basic forms and modes of decoration followed a concise code of execution” (Mester 1990:265). This statement not only confirms my arguments concerning the methodological problems of Estrada’s (1957a, 1957b, 1962) analysis, but confirms the general impression that ceramic vessels are highly standardized across the Manteño territory, despite the regional variation that has been identified through the ethnographic record.

Summary: Geographic and Temporal Variation

Estrada’s work (1957a, 1957b, 1962) is characterized by a proliferation of types based on paste composition or stylistic techniques. Although some geographic variation is suggested by the names of several types (Chanduy, Playas, etc.), the exact geographic

distribution of these types is unknown. Moreover, although a general north-south distinction is suggested in his work, this distinction is based on material culture traits other than ceramics (see Estrada 1962). Finally, the temporal dimensions of the ceramic types he identified remain largely unknown. This is due both to his excavation by arbitrary levels and the absence of radiocarbon dates for his excavations. The picture presented within Estrada's work is largely one of a static ceramic assemblage composed of numerous ceramic types unchanging through time.

Paulsen's work (1970) on the other hand, emphasizes how Manteño forms changed over time. In particular she identifies a gradual transition away from Guangala forms to those present in later Libertad phases. This argument is bolstered by the use of radiocarbon dates, albeit limited, that tie in these ceramic changes not only to an absolute chronology but also to demographic changes on the Peninsula as well. Finally, though Paulsen argues for the specificity of her Libertad assemblage, this distinction appears to be largely semantic. Despite the different nomenclature, by her own admission the Libertad ceramic assemblages appear to be remarkable similar to those present in the northern area of the Manteño territory.

Mester's (1990) analysis is the most complete study of Manteño ceramics to date. Though her chronology is developed from only one site, her comparison of these materials to those recovered by Paulsen suggests that her conclusions may be applicable for the extent of the Manteño territory. Although her sample terminates with an Early Manteño phase, Mester also sees a shift from preceding Guangala forms to those which are recognized as Early Manteño. Further, her inclusion of radiocarbon dates ties these phases into an absolute chronology that can be compared to assemblages in other areas.

Specifically, a comparison between Paulsen's (1970) and Mester's (1990) radiocarbon dates can illuminate questions about the transmission of designs between the northern and southern areas of the Manteño territory. Paulsen's earliest date for Libertad is 1000 A.D. \pm 80, while Mester's earliest date for the workshop is approximately 900 A.D. Alternately, Paulsen's latest Libertad date is 1400 A.D. \pm 100, while Mester's latest is approximately 1300 A.D. This suggests a roughly cotemporaneous use of these ceramic forms in geographically distinct locations, suggesting a close and constant communication between these regions. Future fieldwork is necessary to illuminate the ceramic change that took place in the final one or two hundred years before the arrival of the Spanish.

In summary, these previous ceramic studies suggest that there is little or no evidence of geographic variation in the Manteño ceramic assemblage. Further studies and additional radiocarbon dates may be able to address how these forms and styles spread across the region, but at present there is no information to suggest that the numerous groups described in the ethnohistorical record marked local identity on these ceramics. Rather, it appears that these numerous societies were all engaged in a macro-geographic set of cultural practice that we now call Manteño.

AGUA BLANCA CERAMIC ASSEMBLAGE

The site of Agua Blanca is located 8 kms from the ocean near the neck of the Buenavista river valley (Figure 4.1). There are documented architectural remains from both the Formative and the Integration periods, though no structures have been documented for the intervening periods. Agua Blanca has been identified as the Manteño settlement of Salangome, the principal town of the *Señorío de Salangome*, which is known ethnohistorically as the powerful leader of an ancient League of Merchants (Norton 1986). Archaeological remains attest to its importance as a political and religious center (McEwan 2003).

The data set for this portion of my paper comes from survey conducted by the Proyecto Arqueológico de Valles Interiores del Sur del Manabí (PAVISM) during the 2004 field season at Agua Blanca. Previous extensive survey activities and excavation were undertaken at Agua Blanca in the mid-1980s by Colin McEwan. The PAVISM activities attempted to confirm the sites identified by McEwan, as well as to extend the identification of sites further inland along the Buenavista river valley.

The survey at Agua Blanca was conducted by walking transects at 20 m intervals, walking due north perpendicular to a recorded and mapped footpath. Transects were extended as far as vegetation and topography allowed, generally to the summit of the hills lining the valley. During approximately five weeks of survey, interspersed with excavation, over two hundred transects were completed. The predominant material recovered while on survey was ceramics, though significant amounts of lithic and shell materials were encountered as well.

Figure 4.1 – Map showing the four towns of the *Señorío de Salangome* and the location of Agua Blanca (Salangome) along the Buenavista river valley (McEwan 2003:147).

In my final week at Agua Blanca I recorded a series of measurements taken from the rim sherds recovered while on survey. I was able to record rims from the first fifty transects (1 km) of survey activity, for a total sample of 395 rim sherds. These sherds appear to be representative of those gathered from the approximately 250 transects surveyed during the summer. Although perhaps half a dozen sherds (both bodies and rims) from these 250 transects belong to periods prior to Manteño, the sherds included in this sample are all recognized as Manteño. As they were found on the surface they lack

any context that would give them a relative date. However, based on the presence of both Early and Late Manteño habitation in the valley they likely represent the extent of the Manteño period. Additionally, due to frequent and violent alluvial action in the valley that has deposited significant amounts of soil on Early Manteño settlements (McEwan 2003), it is possible that many sherds are from the Late Manteño period.

The statistical analysis performed on these sherds has two very simple objectives. First, I seek to determine if the classifications we employed for ceramics while in the field were both valid and exclusive. Second, I wish to give formal definition to these categories. This information will be directly applied to subsequent field investigations in the coming years, and will allow me to address questions of temporal and geographical differences that form the core of the second half of the thesis.

In-Field Classification

The criteria and method for classifying ceramics while in the field were developed by Dr. Jan Olson (University of Alberta) and Freddy Acuña, based in part on ceramic types identified by the early work of Estrada (1957a, 1957b, 1962) and confirmed by Acuña's many years practicing archaeology in coastal Ecuador. The method of classification was based on ceramic classifications performed by Dr. Olson during her dissertation work at the Postclassic sites of Capilco, Cuexcomate, and Yautepec in Moreles, Mexico (2001).

Ceramics were classified first by vessel form. Forms identified in the field primarily included *cuencos* (bowls), *cazuelas* (large bowls or basins), *jarras* (jars), *botellas* (bottles), *compoteras*, *comales*, *ollas*, and *cantarillas* (Figure 4.2). Once the

vessel form had been identified, sherds were separated into distinct numbered categories that identified both paste color and presence or absence of polish, and often included particular forms of decoration (examples include *jarra pulido negro con lineas finas* [black polished jar with fine line decoration], *jarra pulido rojo* [red polished jar], and *jarra no pulido* [unpolished jar]). Finally, sherds within these categories were separated as body, rim, or base sherds.

Figure 4.2 – Vessel forms classified in analysis.

The value of this system of classification lies in its ready adaptation as new types of ceramics were brought in from survey. A possible drawback lies in its conflation of several aspects of ceramic technology into one category, such as paste color and decoration techniques. Although all ceramics were classified under this rubric in the field, I took measurements on rim sherds to determine if the forms identified are indeed the only ones present in the ceramic assemblage, as well as to determine if the classifications we made in the field can be supported by statistical analysis of different attributes of the ceramic technology.

Measurements

The measurements I took of Manteño rim sherds fall into three main categories: *formal*, *fabric*, and *design*. The formal category includes measurements of the inner and outer rim diameter (coded as ID and OD, respectively), as well as the inner and outer angles of the rim (coded as IA and OA, respectively). Diameter measurements were taken on a standard diameter board, and record the outer and inner extremes of the rim. Angle measurements were taken by finding the point where the rim “sits” and measuring angle at which the rim falls away from this point on both the inside and outside of this point (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3 – Graphical representation of formal measurements taken on vessel rims.

Fabric measures included paste color (PC), size of paste inclusions (PI), the presence or absence of polish (PO), the presence or absence of slip (S), and slip color (SC). Paste color and slip color were both measured as ordinal variables in general color categories (1-dark grey (black), 2- dark brown, 3- red, 4- light brown (cream), 5- light

Decoration	1	Excised
	2	Incised
	3	Applique
Designs	1	Solid
	2	Wide lined
	3	Thin lined
	4	Circles
	5	Circular Spirals
	6	Square Spirals
	7	Hatch Marks
	8	Triangular Spirals
	9	Figure (anthropomorphic or zoomorphic)
	10	Rays
	11	Triangles

Table 4.1 – Design categories utilized in the analysis of rim sherds from Agua Blanca.

grey). These numbers were assigned following the pattern presented in Munsell color charts according to color value, a measure of color lightness, where 1 is darkest (Munsell 1975). The presence or absence of polish or slip were assessed as nominal variables.

The size of paste inclusions was assessed as an ordinal variable on a scale as 0- no visible inclusions, 1- small visible inclusions, 2-large visible inclusions.

Design categories included additional vessel treatments, including fine line painting or incised designs. Different decorative treatments were assigned a number, as was each design element. While a vessel generally had only one decorative treatment, several had numerous design elements. A vessel was given a number for each design element present. These numbers are presented in Table 4.1. These designs, though not all present on sherds in the sample, were observed on other sherds in the course of summer classification.

Description of Sample

A complete list of cases and corresponding variables is presented in Appendix A. This sample of 395 rims is dominated by ollas (n=193). These ollas are generally composed of a dark reddish brown paste with large, often pebble sized, inclusions. My general impression was that, while there was some variation in the flare of the rim, olla rims were highly standardized in their width, approximately 6cms in width. Several ollas possessed rims with finger applied red slip. In Mester's sample (1990), these red-slipped rim ollas were characteristic of vessels in the earliest phase recovered from Los Frailes. Three possibilities may account for their presence at Agua Blanca: 1) these vessels represent evidence of an Early Manteño ceramic assemblage; 2) these vessels may be a slight form of archaism that are revived in later time periods; 3) these vessels may represent a special function vessel, such as burial urns, that were only used in early phases of the Los Frailes workshop but which may have been used over a broader time

span in other areas of the Manteño territory. Further research is required to test these possibilities.

The second most frequent vessel form is jars (n=93). Jar forms are present in all five paste colors, though are most common in red, light brown, and light grey. In general they have small or no visible paste inclusions. These jar forms, often referred to as *bell-rim jars*, are characterized by broad, gradually flaring rims. They are generally polished and sometimes possess geometric burnished designs. Though not present in the sherds analyzed here, jars often have modeled anthropomorphic or zoomorphic faces, *mascarones*, applied to the neck of the vessel.

Bottle forms, while comprising a small portion of the sample (n=9) are closely related to jar forms in their shape and paste. Indeed, it was often difficult to differentiate between these two forms in the field. In general, bottles tend to be made of a finer paste than jars. Additionally, their necks are generally narrower and the rims flare out almost horizontally from the neck. The bottles in this sample are made of several different paste colors, the most frequent of which is the light grey paste. Bottles are frequently polished and often have areas of burnished designs.

The comals present in this sample (n=33) correspond to the *ralladores manabita* originally identified by Estrada (1957a, 1957b, 1962) and confirmed by Paulsen (1970) and Mester (1990). The vast majority of comals are made of a red paste with small inclusions. They represent cooking griddles or coarse serving plates. Comals consist of three types. The first, identified simply as plates by Mester (1990), have smooth surfaces. The second, identified as *comales en lineas* by our summer classification, has straight lines running along the bottom, often intersecting at right angles, forming

triangles of straight lines as if the potters dragged their fingers through wet clay. The final type, formed in this same manner, were identified as *comales curveadas* by our summer classifications. As these designs are present on the base of the comals and often not visible on the rim, no effort was made to differentiate between these three different types in my analysis.

Compoteras (n=33), or pedestal plates, are made from a variety of paste colors, but are generally made of clays with small or non-visible paste inclusions. They are most often polished and occasionally possess burnished designs. Compoteras could have served two functions, acting either as fine ware serving plates or as incense burners.

The sample also contains several bowl rims (n=29), most commonly direct walled hemispherical bowls. While these are made of several different paste colors, the vast majority are polished. Bowls are the most highly decorated form in the sample, including both incised and excised designs. These bowls were likely serving ware of some sort, possibly for chicha.

There are two remaining form types in this sample. Cazuelas (n=4) are unpolished vessels, and in this sample all are made of dark brown paste. They appear to be coarse cooking vessels, like ollas. The major difference between cazuelas and ollas is that cazuelas are direct walled vessels with large openings at the mouth. Cantarillas (n=1) are generally very well made fine wares, highly polished, and without visible paste inclusions. These elliptical shaped vessels have very restricted openings. It is possible that some may have been used as lime pots, though there is no evidence of residue on the one rim sherd in this sample.

Discriminant Analysis

Discriminant analysis is a multivariate statistical technique in which several independent variables are used to describe the group compositions of one dependent variable (Baxter 1994). As in principal component and correspondence analysis, factors are created as new variables to account for the variance in the sample. In discriminant analysis however, these linear combinations of the variables are created to account for difference between the previously known groups included in the dependant variable (Baxter 1994).

Discriminant analysis can be used for several purposes, including: “to confirm that the presumed groups are indeed distinct; to characterize the groups on the basis of the coefficients associated with the linear combinations of the variables; to identify individuals that do not readily fit into their presumed group; to identify those variables that best discriminate between groups, or to provide a criterion for allocating unclassified individuals to a group” (Baxter 1994:186).

Discriminant analysis has found application within archaeology, particularly to validate classifications of various types of artifacts (Baxter 1994, 2003). It is to that end that I use discriminant analysis here. In particular, I am concerned to assess if vessel form categories we used to classify ceramic materials in the field are valid and exclusive. If they are, the independent variables (diameters, angles, paste color, etc.) should be able to correctly sort the 395 cases into the eight vessel types contained within the dependent variable “form”. Furthermore, I am interested in assessing to what degree different variables are most useful in distinguishing between different vessel form types. Finally, on the basis of discriminant analysis I will give formal definitions to these vessel types.

Discriminant Analysis was performed in SPSS, student version 11, using the stepwise method. The cantarilla (n=1) and cazuela (n=4) forms were excluded from analysis due to the small size of the samples. The stepwise method analyzes the variables included in the data set to determine which are most appropriate for separating cases into the proper categories. In this sample, the formal and fabric variables described above were analyzed for affiliation with different form categories. From this stepwise discriminant analysis four variables were excluded: outer diameter, paste color, presence or absence of slip, and slip color. Five variables were retained: presence or absence of polish, inner angle, inner diameter, outer diameter, and paste inclusions.

Some preliminary observations are possible simply based on those variables included and excluded from this analysis. The exclusion of slip color tells us little as it is a dependent variable; slip color is predicated upon the presence of slip. However, the exclusion of paste color suggests that vessel shape is of greater significance than vessel color in the creation of different vessel forms. The implication is that aesthetic concerns were perhaps secondary to the functional characteristics of the vessel. This is an important note, as it suggests that Estrada's (1957a, 1957b, 1962) emphasis on paste to determine vessel types is misfounded. Alternately, the presence of different paste colors used for the same vessel forms may indicate objects brought to Agua Blanca through trade or pilgrimage. A third possibility is that these variations in paste and slip color indicate personal preference or different intended uses of the vessels. Only future research involving chemical sourcing of ceramics can determine this.

Second, although paste color is excluded from the analysis, the coarseness of paste inclusions is retained. This mirrors the emphasis on functional characteristics of

different vessel forms, in which the fabric of the paste is more important than the color of the paste. This suggests that while potters were flexible in their use of clay sources, the natural inclusions in these sources or the careful addition of tempering agents was important for the production of different vessel forms. Alternately, paste color may have important implications for the intended use of the vessel, uses which are currently beyond the understanding of the archaeologists. Further work involving the chemical analysis and identification of clay sources, as well as detailed analysis of tempering agents may reveal which of these possibilities was pursued by Manteño potters.

Finally, the exclusion of the variable “Outer Angle” suggests that there was significant variety used to shape the rim. Thus while the general form of the vessel was highly standardized, the shape or flare of the rim was not. This could indicate the personal preference of the potter or a special vessel function that specialized the standard form. Again, future research is necessary to examine these possibilities.

A second discriminant analysis was performed, analyzing only those five variables identified by the stepwise method. The split-halves method was used to validate the analysis, in which a discriminant model was developed for 195 of the vessel rims and then tested against the remaining 195 rims. These 195 vessels were chosen as a random sample within SPSS using the select cases function.

Wilks’ Lambda represents the amount of variance in the sample not accounted for by the linear combinations of variables (Tabachnick and Fidell 1983). Thus, the smaller the value of Wilk’s Lamba for an independent variable, the greater amount of variance within the sample that the variable covers. In this sample, Wilk’s Lambda (Table 4.2) indicates that the variable “Polish” contributed most significantly to the discriminant

function, followed by “Inner Diameter”, “Paste Inclusions”, “Outer Diameter”, and “Inner Angle”, respectively.

	Wilks' Lambda	F	Df1	Df2	Sig.
OD	.520	19.663	5	189	.000
ID	.453	29.668	5	189	.000
IA	.676	12.484	5	189	.000
PI	.501	28.212	5	189	.000
PO	.420	65.150	5	189	.000

Table 4.2 – Wilks' Lambda from SPSS discriminant analysis.

Box's M tests the null hypothesis that the covariance matrices do not differ between groups formed by the dependent variable, in this case form. At a significance of 0.00 the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that the covariance matrices do differ. While this violates an assumption of discriminant analysis, in large samples, such as this one, even a small variation in the sample can be found significant, and thus the discriminant analysis may still be robust (Tabachnick and Fidell 1983).

Five functions were produced for the sample, of which only the first two are used. These two variables account for 96.9% of the cumulative variance of the sample (Table 4.3). The first function alone accounts for almost two thirds of the entire variance in the sample, making it a strong predictor of group membership.

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	2.361	63.5	63.5	.838
2	1.241	33.4	96.9	.744
3	.079	2.1	99.0	.271
4	.031	.8	99.9	.174
5	.005	.1	100.0	.074

Table 4.3 – Eigenvalues and percent of variance for five factors produced by SPSS discriminant analysis.

The Structure Matrix presented below (Table 4.4) shows the correlation of each variable with each discriminant function produced by SPSS. This matrix is used to assign meaning to each factor used in the analysis. The variable with the largest absolute value contributes most significantly to that factor. Factor 1 loads most heavily on the variable “Polish”, indicating that Factor 1 is roughly a measure of the presence or absence of polish on the vessel, though “Inner Diameter” loads relatively heavily on Factor 1 as well. The importance of polish in this analysis suggests that it is possible to divide vessels into two categories based on the presence or absence of polish, a category of unpolished coarse or utilitarian wares, and a category of polished finewares. This mirrors Mester’s (1990) observation for her Los Frailes sample.

	Function	
	1	2
PO	-.708	.370
ID	.692	.240
OD	.618	-.047
PI	.612	-.257
IA	.231	.525

Table 4.4 – Structure Matrix showing the correlations between variables and functions. The highest absolute value indicates the relative weight of each variable for a function.

Factor 2 loads most heavily onto the variable “Inner Angle”. The effect of these Factors is visible in the canonical discriminant function scatter plot (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4 – Scatter plot depicting the function value of each case.

These two factors create four quadrants, in which the centroids of each vessel form are clearly delineated. The upper right quadrant corresponds to unpolished vessels with a mean Inner Angle measure greater than 45 degrees. The lower right quadrant corresponds to unpolished vessels with a mean Inner Angle measure less than 45 degrees. The lower left quadrant corresponds to polished vessels with a mean Inner Angle measure less than 45 degrees. Finally, the upper left quadrant corresponds to polished vessels with a mean Inner Angle measure greater than 45 degrees.

The discriminant analysis produced using the split-halves method is very robust, achieving a 83.1% rate of correct classification for the 195 cases included, as well as for the 195 cases not included (Table 4.5).

			Predicted Group Membership						
		Form	Bottle	Comal	Compotera	Cuenco	Jar	Olla	Total
Cases Selected	Count	Bottle	0	0	1	0	6	0	7
		Comal	0	8	1	0	0	2	11
		Compotera	0	1	13	1	2	2	19
		Cuenco	0	1	4	4	0	0	9
		Jar	0	0	3	0	41	8	52
		Olla	0	0	0	0	1	96	97
	%	Bottle	0	0	14.3	0	85.7	0	100
		Comal	0	72.7	9.1	0	0	18.2	100
		Compotera	0	5.3	68.4	5.3	10.5	10.5	100
		Cuenco	0	11.1	44.4	44.4	0	0	100
		Jar	0	0	5.8	0	78.8	15.4	100
		Olla	0	0	0	0	1.0	99.0	100
Cases Not Selected	Count	Bottle	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
		Comal	0	19	0	0	0	3	22
		Compotera	0	0	11	0	2	1	14
		Cuenco	0	0	12	6	0	2	20
		Jar	0	1	2	0	36	2	41
		Olla	0	3	3	0	0	90	96
	%	Bottle	0	0	0	0	100	0	100
		Comal	0	86.4	0	0	0	13.6	100
		Compotera	0	0	78.6	0	14.3	7.1	100
		Cuenco	0	0	60.0	30.0	0	10.0	100
		Jar	0	2.4	4.9	0	87.8	4.9	100
		Olla	0	3.1	3.1	0	0	93.8	100

Table 4.5 – Summary table depicting the classification of each case.

Bottle forms are, without fail, misclassified, most commonly as jars. This may be due in part to the small number available for this sample. Indeed, we had difficulty at times in separating bottle and jar fragments while in the field. We developed criteria to differentiate these forms, but the results of this analysis suggest that these criteria may have been more in the minds of the investigators than in the vessel itself. Based on these results I would suggest classifying bottles as a sub-type of the jar form, but not as a distinct category itself.

Comal forms were clearly distinct in this analysis. A few cases were identified incorrectly as ollas, though I would suggest that this is due to their mutual absence of polish that is so important to the analysis.

Although compotera forms are fairly well distinguished in this analysis, there is some spread of compotera cases into other form categories, particularly the bowl and jar category, but the comal category as well. I would suggest that some of the spread into the jar and bowl categories is based on the presence of polish in all three forms. The spread into the comal category is likely due to the similar shape of the vessels. Although there is this spread, I would argue that the compotera form is a unique one, particularly in the context of field identification.

The bowl form is less clearly identified. It is divided almost equally into the bowl and compotera categories. I would argue that this is due to the presence of polish on both forms, as well as similarities in the shape of the rim, particularly the inner angle of the rim. Although these categories thus overlap, bowl forms are still readily identified in the field. Further, bowls are more frequently embellished with incised and excised designs.

While these designs were not included in the discriminant analysis due to their relative rarity in the sample as a whole, I do discuss them below.

The jar form is another coherent category confirmed by discriminant analysis. While there is some overlap in the compotera form category, as there is compotera overlap in the jar form, I believe most of this is explained by the presence of polish on both vessel types. Additionally, the misclassification of several jars as ollas are likely those few vessels that are unpolished jars, perhaps representing jars used to carry or store water, forming a utilitarian component of this otherwise fine ware vessel type.

Finally, ollas form the most distinct vessel form of the entire sample. This may be due in part to their large number in the sample, providing the discriminant program more data with which to define the variables. Regardless, this mirrors the ubiquitous nature of this form within the assemblage recovered in the field, and its clear difference from other vessel form types.

Overall, the discriminant analysis supports the classifications that we made within the field. While this analysis suggests that bottles should be considered as a sub-type of the jar form, the other vessel forms identified in the field have been supported by analysis. Finally, the importance of polish (based on the eigenvalue of Factor 1) in identifying vessel form suggests that body sherds may be successfully classified in 65% of the cases based simply on the presence or absence of polish.

Designs

Relatively few of the rims included in this sample possessed any kind of decoration. The only vessels displaying decoration are those that fall into the category of polished

finewares. One bottle (n=9) had pattern burnished designs in the form of wide lines and cross hatching. Three compoteras (n=33) possessed pattern burnished designs, primarily composed of solid areas of burnishing and wide or thin lines (Figure 4.5). One compotera was painted with a stylized anthropomorphic face (Figure 4.6). This was the only such design recovered from our survey activities in the summer 2004 field season.

Figure 4.5 – Compotera with pattern burnished designs of solid areas, wide lines, and fine lines (Agua Blanca, Manabí, Ecuador).

Figure 4.6 – Compotera with anthropomorphic face (Agua Blanca, Manabí, Ecuador).

Five bowls (n=29) bore designs. One was a pattern burnished design of solid areas and thin lines while the remaining four were excised designs (Figure 4.7). These excised designs are frequently elaborate and cover the body of the vessel. Two bowls were excised to create wide lines and a ray design, while another was excised to create wide lines and circular spirals. The fourth contained a complex design of wide lines, square spirals, rays, and triangles.

Finally, fourteen jars (n=93) had designs. Two possessed incised designs, one with hatch marks and the other with thin lines. The remaining twelve had pattern

burnished designs of solid areas, wide lines, thin lines, and hatch marks. Hatch marks were generally paired with one of the more basic forms.

Figure 4.7 – Excised Bowl Designs (Agua Blanca, Manabí, Ecuador).

Overall, vessels with designs formed a very small component of the sample (n=24, 6%). Pattern burnished designs compose the most frequent form of decoration, and hatch marks are commonly paired with solid areas of burnishing or with wide or thin lines. Bowls, primarily of the black ware type that the Manteño are known for, possess a more varied repertoire of designs.

Compared to previous ceramic studies, particularly that of Mester (1990), the pattern burnished designs in this sample are virtually identical, though her study illustrates a greater variety of designs. The incised and excised designs, on the other hand, are underrepresented in both Mester's sample (1990) and Paulsen's (1970), making comparison difficult. Despite the small sample, the general theme of the designs is similar, particularly in comparison to the designs depicted in Paulsen (1970).

Summary

The discriminant analysis performed using data collected from the 2004 field season at Agua Blanca reveals that, based on the measurements taken, vessel forms can be identified with 83.1% accuracy. Further, this analysis reveals that the ceramic assemblage is composed of two distinct classes of vessels, fine wares and coarse wares, which are distinguished by the presence or absence of polish.

Vessels were further distinguished in discriminant analysis based on the internal angle of the rim. Examination of the data in Appendix A reveals that even this measure varies widely within any given form. Although discriminant analysis does not reveal vessel sub-types, it is possible that, with a larger sample or one with temporal differentiation, that sub-types may be revealed.

It is particularly clear from the scatter plot of rims that the bottle and jar vessel categories overlap significantly. Likewise, the compotera and bowl forms have similar centroids. It is possible that this overlap is due to the small sizes of the vessel categories. I would particularly argue for this interpretation for the compotera and bowl forms, as the complete vessel shapes are very different. Bottles, on the other hand, were often difficult to identify in the field, and thus may best be treated as a sub-type of jars.

Compared to the previous ceramic studies in the region, particularly those of Mester (1990) and Paulsen (1970), the ceramic remains from Agua Blanca appear identical to those from Libertad and, in particular, to those from Los Frailes. This suggests that the ceramics from Agua Blanca can 1) be classified using previously existing classificatory schemes, particularly that devised by Mester (1990), and 2) that the Agua Blanca remains, and thus the site, may be considered part of the previously defined

Manteño culture. This similarity, however, indicates that the ethnic differences described in Section III are not reflected in the ceramic remains. The implications of this will be discussed in the following section.

SECTION V - CONCLUSIONS

Despite investigations spanning more than one hundred years, the archaeology of coastal Ecuador is still largely in its infancy. A detailed culture-history is still need for many regions and time periods. Further, a processual understanding of the transformation of one recognized archaeological culture into another is greatly needed.

Archaeological examinations of style have primarily been conducted to infer social identity (Stark 1998). Similarities in stylistic elements have been interpreted as a reflection of extensive cultural contact and interaction. Conversely, stylistic differences have been interpreted as reflecting group boundaries, either at the meta, cultural, level, or at the smaller, ethnic level of group affiliation. Thus, a continuum has been proposed, with similarity and contact at one end, and difference and sub-group affiliation at the other.

Within Manteño society, ample evidence exists not only for the presence of extensive trade networks, but also for the existence of regional identities, possibly ethnicity. Maritime trade networks extended north to Mexico and south to Peru, exchanging craft goods for *Spondylus* in Mexico, and *Spondylus* for copper in Peru. Within ancient Ecuador there existed a quasi-market economy that circulated a variety of goods from different ecological zones into others. Although the nature of this trade is not known for the Manteño region, symbiotic relationships between fishermen and agriculturists circulated comestibles within localized political entities (Silva 1984).

The broader Manteño region has been subdivided into three areas with distinct, though occasionally not well defined, political structures. The Punáes on Isla Puná were organized in seven chiefdoms, ruled over by a supreme chief. The Huancavilcas, located

on the Santa Elena Peninsula and around the modern city of Guayaquil, were likely composed of several different chiefdoms, though this political structure is not well defined in the literature. Finally, in the northern region of the Manteño territory, what might be termed “Manteño Proper” were four chiefdoms, likely organized into a League of Merchants. There is some evidence within the ethnohistoric record that these people conceived of themselves as distinct entities, and may be usefully conceptualized as ethnicities.

By reviewing previous ceramic studies (Estrada 1957a, 1957b; Mester 1990; Paulsen 1970) I have shown that ceramics vary little across the broad Manteño region. Further, I have added the data from the site of Agua Blanca to this comparative exercise, and those data reaffirm that minimal ceramic differentiation existed in the Manteño material remains.

I have argued that the ceramic assemblage shows no evidence that it reflects the social groups known historically, but I do not rule out the utility in examining these ceramic remains for evidence of these social boundaries. I suggest instead that our emphasis on stylistic variation may be too facile for a detailed reading of Manteño ceramics. Alternative investigations, such as an examination of ceramic technology through the *chaîne opératoire* approach, may reveal the *habitus* of potters and the social boundaries that accompanied these practice (Stark 1998).

A final conclusion is possible. Although we can conclude that the Manteño ceramic assemblage was remarkably homogenous, this is not to say that people did not mark regional or local identities. It may mean, however, that *how* they marked their regional identities may be beyond the reach of archaeology. Jijón y Caamaño (1941)

suggests that these groups were distinguished by mutually unintelligible languages.

Further, the group differences may have actually been inscribed onto the body, either in the design and manner of clothing, or in modifications made to the body. A passage written by Cieza de León suggests that this may indeed be the case:

On this coast and land subject to the city of Puerto Viejo and that of Guayaquil there are two types of people¹, because from Cape Passao and the Santiago river as far [south] as the town of Salango the men have worked [tattooed] faces, and the design begins from just below and above the ear and descends to the beard [the chin], the width being a matter of individual preference...because some embellish nearly the whole face and others less almost the same way in which the Moors decorate themselves. The women of these Indians are likewise adorned and dressed and they and their husbands have cloaks and shirts of cotton, and some of wool... and the principal towns where the inhabitants are tattooed in this province are: Pasaos, Xaramixo, Pimpanguace, Peclansemeque, and the valley of Xagua, Pechonse, and those of Monte-Cristo, Apechigue and Silos, and Caniloha and Manta and Zopil, Manavi, Xaraguaza and others (Cieza de León 1962 [1553]:151, as translated in McEwan 2003).

Although many of the towns listed in this passage cannot be identified, those that can be identified lie near the modern town of Puerto Viejo in the area identified as the Manteño heartland in section Two. This practice of tattooing, apparently conducted by both men and women, is visible on several Manteño figurines and vessels (Figure 5.1). The prominent facial tattooing, whether used to mark initiation or regional affiliation, nonetheless appear to have a marked regional quality, which would have served to mark these individuals as northern Manteños (or Salangomeños, or Jocayans, or Picoazaños, etc.) from afar. Unfortunately, due to the poor conditions of preservation in coastal Ecuador, these possible markers of identity will never be recovered. An alternative line

¹ The other group not mentioned in this section of the text lived further inland, and likely corresponds to the Milagro-Quevedo archaeological culture.

of inquiry could examine the figurines and vessels that depict tattooing and through chemical analysis determine if there is a pattern to use of these designs.

Figure 5.1 – Manteño figurines depicting facial tattooing: a. Museo Chileno de Arte Precolombino, b. Bushnell (1951:105).

Essentially, I am arguing that a multitude of regional groups, perhaps ethnicities, were engaged in a broad trading network that brought them into intimate contact with people of different groups. In these situations, as a certain degree of differentiation existed in terms of language or body markings, ceramics were a means through which a broad group of people could express a shared background or interest. Until the production aspect of Manteño ceramics is better understood, my conclusion remains an educated guess. However, it appears that mutual understanding in situations of contact through trade was the deciding factor in the manufacture of Manteño ceramics.

Future Directions

From the discussion above, two areas appear that require further research. First, there is a need to build a ceramic chronology for the later centuries of Manteño habitation on the coast. This will not only provide an account of how the ceramic assemblage continued to change, but will also reflect more accurately the materials used by the social groups that the Spanish recorded. Second, chemical analyses and sourcing of ceramic vessels may not only illuminate localized variations in ceramic assemblages, but can also be used to reconstruct the systems of trade and exchange in which the Manteño engaged.

In the end, our inability to answer the question of Manteño regional sub-traditions may lie more in our conception of the problem than in the ability of the archaeological record to answer it. Rather than studying a Manteño culture and asking where and how the dividing lines were conceptualized and created, perhaps we should be studying the Punáes, the Huancavilcas, the Salangomeños, and the Jocayans, and building a basic knowledge base about the subsistence, settlement pattern, socio-political organization, and ideology of these individual groups. Once a basic knowledge about each of these entities has been built, then we may begin to look at the ways in which these different groups and different areas negotiated their interaction, creating the “differentiated-yet-homogenous” slippery entity that archaeologists refer to as Manteño.

APPENDIX

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
41	5	bot	21	13	5	160	1	0	0	1	5					
41	5	bot	21	8	10	150	2	0	1	1	4	2	7			
6	3	bot	22	18	10	160	4	0	1	1	4					
5	2	bot	22	16	1	5	5	0	1	1	5					
36	1.5	bot	24	20	40	130	5	0	1	1	5					
41	4.5	bot	18	11	15	150	5	0	1	1	3					
47	2	bot	18	12	5	160	5	0	1	1	5					
36	2	bot	17	5	20	140	5	1	1	1	1					
47	2	bot	19	11	30	10	5	1	1	1	2					
TC	1	cant	8	8	150	20	5	0	1	1	1					
42	3	cm	37	35	60	110	1	1	0	0						
43	3	cm	38	37	60	105	1	1	0	1	3					
49	8	cm	37	36	125	45	2	1	0	0						
39	3M1	cm	45	45	110	60	2	1	0	0						
39	4	cm	37	37	100	80	2	1	0	0						
39	4	cm	38	38	70	110	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	cm	50	50	115	50	2	1	0	0						
41	4	cm	33	32	120	45	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	cm	37	35	95	100	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	cm	28	28	40	130	2	1	0	0						
42	7	cm	32	32	45	125	2	1	0	0						
43	3	cm	58	56	75	100	2	1	0	0						
45	2_E1	cm	30	30	105	65	2	1	0	0						
45	2_E2	cm	38	38	115	60	2	1	0	0						
49	3	cm	40	39	85	75	2	1	0	0						
49	3	cm	32	32	65	115	2	1	0	0						
43	5	cm	42	42	50	115	2	1	0	0						
48	3	cm	51	50	50	115	2	1	0	1	3					
36	2	cm	30	27	20	40	2	2	0	1	3					
40	3.5	cm	42	42	120	40	2	2	0	0						
40	6	cm	40	40	60	110	2	2	0	0						
45	2_E2	cm	42	41	55	110	2	2	0	0						
49	3	cm	38	36	90	50	2	2	0	0						
5	2	cm	25	23	5	140	3	0	0	0						
41	3.5	cm	18	17	70	10	3	0	1	1	3					
36	1	cm	30	25	20	100	3	1	0	0						
TC	23	cm	51	50	120	50	3	1	0	0						
43	3	cm	26	24	70	80	3	1	0	0						
49	0	cm	41	40	85	75	3	1	0	0						
43	3	cm	48	46	95	60	4	1	0	0						
48	1	cm	38	38	80	70	5	1	0	0						
41	2	cm	25	24	65	110	5	1	0	1	4					
43	3	cm	29	27	60	80	5	2	0	0						
5	2	cp	24	21	5	130	1	1	1	1	3					
49	1	cp	28	15	60	160	2	0	1	1	3					
42	3	cp	23	21	45	90	2	1	1	1	1					
32	1	cp	30	30	50	110	2	1	1	0						
43	5	cp	28	25	90	110	2	1	1	1	3					
13	4	cp	38	36	40	40	2	2	0	0						
47	7	cp	28	26	150	40	2	2	0	0						
41	4	cp	38	35	85	85	3	0	1	1	3					
42	1	cp	26	24	20	10	3	0	1	1	1					
35	4	cp	11	11	60	100	3	0	1	1	3					
47	7	cp	32	30	60	40	3	1	0	0						
41	5	cp	28	25	75	120	3	1	1	1	3					
46	0	cp	22	20	70	110	3	1	1	1	3					
33	2	cp	26	25	50	110	3	1	1	1	3					
41	2	cp	26	26	80	85	4	0	1	1	1					

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
43	3	cp	22	19	85	100	4	0	1	1	4					
TC	12	cp	19	19	60	110	4	1	1	1	3	3	9			
46	5	cp	18	10	25	145	5	0	0	0						
4	8	cp	30	23	70	70	5	0	1	1	5	2				
34	6	cp	24	22	30	70	5	0	1	1	5					
36	1.5	cp	37	31	60	40	5	0	1	1	1					
41	3.5	cp	25	22	100	50	5	0	1	1	3					
43	1	cp	24	22	55	115	5	0	1	1	3					
46	7	cp	19	16	40	85	5	0	1	1	1					
41	5	cp	18	16	70	120	5	0	1	1	1					
46	4	cp	36	34	50	110	5	0	1	1	3					
49	3	cp	25	23	65	105	5	0	1	1	1					
25	6	cp	32	28	40	130	5	1	0	0						
TC	7	cp	26	23	70	100	5	1	1	1	2	2				
TC	13	cp	29	28	30	140	5	1	1	1	5	1	3			
43	1	cp	28	26	60	110	5	1	1	1	5					
48	2	cp	37	30	10	10	5	1	1	1	2					
6	2	cp	34	31	60	40	5	2	1	1	5					
43	3	cue	21	21	70	100	1	0	0	0						
41	3.5	cue	20	20	60	105	1	0	1	1	1					
37	3	cue	18	17	60	105	1	0	1	1	1					
14	1.5	cue	24	24	80	95	1	1	1	0						
14	1.5	cue	25	25	70	100	1	1	1	1	3					
41	3	cue	30	29	75	95	1	2	1	1	3					
49	1	cue	9	8	85	85	2	0	1	1	1	2				
49	1	cue	18	17	80	80	2	0	1	1	3					
42	4.5	cue	22	19	20	160	2	1	1	1	4					
46	7	cue	20	20	50	120	3	0	1	1	5					
42	6	cue	14	14	105	85	3	0	1	1	2					
8	3	cue	15	15	70	100	3	1	0	0						
38	4	cue	31	31	45	120	3	1	0	0						
40	2	cue	30	26	60	20	3	1	0	1	3					
41	5	cue	17	15	85	85	3	1	0	0						
47	3	cue	17	13	30	140	3	2	0	0						
41	7	cue	24	23	70	100	4	0	1	1	4	2	5			1
48	9.5	cue	18	17	85	85	4	0	1	1	4					
TC	10	cue	26	26	85	80	4	1	1	1	2	2	6	10	11	1
42	6	cue	30	25	20	20	4	1	1	1	1	1	3			
33	2	cue	20	19	60	105	5	0	0	1	3					
37	3	cue	24	21	80	95	5	0	1	1	1	2	10			1
47	8	cue	36	33	85	170	5	0	1	1	4					
48	1	cue	27	27	75	95	5	0	1	1	5					
42	6	cue	14	14	60	105	5	0	1	1	5					
45	2_E2	cue	20	20	110	95	5	0	1	1	4					
40	8	cue	25	22	10	150	5	1	1	1	3					
TC	15	cue	20	17	95	20	5	1	1	1	2	2	10			1
48	3	cue	19	17	10	170	5	1	1	1	4					
37	3	cz	42	36	75	10	2	1	0	0						
39	4	cz	40	37	10	80	2	2	0	1	3					
TC	45	cz	43	39	40	120	2	2	0	0						
46	5	cz	60	57	50	100	2	2	0	0						
41	3.5	jar	18	12	40	130	1	0	0	0						
43	3	jar	21	13	20	150	1	0	1	1	1	7				2
45	1	jar	27	20	30	120	1	0	1	1	1					
36	1	jar	32	22	30	130	1	1	0	0						
35	2	jar	21	17	50	110	1	1	1	1	5					
35	3	jar	26	14	30	125	1	1	1	1	5					
49	1.5	jar	21	13	55	105	1	1	1	1	2					

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
27	3	jar	24	18	50	115	2	0	1	1	3					
42	1	jar	23	19	50	140	2	0	1	1	2					
43	3	jar	28	16	25	145	2	0	1	1	3					
42	3	jar	18	14	30	120	2	1	0	0						
43	5	jar	18	9	25	140	2	1	0	0						
49	3	jar	32	30	20	155	2	1	0	1	3					
47	7	jar	25	13	15	150	2	1	0	0						
49	8	jar	16	7	30	135	2	1	1	1	2					
43	1	jar	24	16	10	150	2	1	1	1	2					
35	2	jar	25	19	20	150	3	0	1	1	3					
36	1.5	jar	15	7	20	150	3	0	1	1	3					
40	1	jar	36	30	20	140	3	0	1	1	5					
12	4	jar	19	15	30	135	3	0	1	0						
45	0	jar	23	17	40	115	3	1	0	0						
49	2	jar	24	23	100	60	3	1	0	0						
41	5.5	jar	28	20	20	145	3	1	0	1	3					
13	4	jar	23	19	40	120	3	1	1	0						
34	10	jar	35	30	30	130	3	1	1	1	3					
37	2	jar	27	17	30	130	3	1	1	0						
37	2	jar	18	12	30	10	3	1	1	1	3	3				2
43	3	jar	24	16	10	150	3	1	1	1	3					
43	4	jar	28	22	10	150	3	1	1	1	3	2	3			
45	2_E1	jar	18	10	20	150	3	1	1	1	4					
31	7	jar	22	16	40	110	3	2	0	0						
10	1	jar	20	12	20	140	3	2	1	1	4					
42	4.5	jar	21	8	20	140	3	2	1	1	3					
42	1	jar	21	16	35	125	4	0	0	1	2					
43	1	jar	18	10	20	140	4	0	0	0						
47	7	jar	19	8	25	20	4	0	1	1	3					
42	2	jar	23	15	20	140	4	0	1	1	4	2	7			
43	1	jar	26	14	5	155	4	0	1	1	4					
46	0	jar	30	25	25	140	4	0	1	1	4					
TC	43	jar	21	8	30	140	4	0	1	1	1					
42	6	jar	15	11	10	150	4	0	1	1	3					
40	1	jar	26	19	20	145	4	0	1	1	4					
49	3	jar	24	14	15	155	4	0	1	1	1					
44	3.50E+01	jar	21	8	10	150	4	1	1	1	4					
TC	14	jar	21	8	10	155	4	1	1	1	1	1	7			
48	2	jar	21	7	10	155	4	1	1	1	4					
42	6	jar	28	20	5	155	4	1	1	1	4					
49	1	jar	20	8	20	145	4	1	1	1	4	2	3	7		
44	2	jar	23	13	10	155	4	1	1	1	1					
49	3	jar	21	8	20	150	4	1	1	1	1					
48	4	jar	27	16	20	140	5	0	0	1	3					
43	4	jar	10	8	10	110	5	0	0	1	4					
43	4	jar	27	21	30	140	5	0	0	0						
TC	33	jar	21	8	15	150	5	0	0	1	5	2	3	7		
45	2_E2	jar	21	9	10	150	5	0	0	0						
47	9	jar	18	9	15	150	5	0	0	0						
35	2	jar	12	8	40	120	5	0	1	1	4					
39	3M1	jar	21	11	30	130	5	0	1	1	5	3				
40	2	jar	22	16	30	130	5	0	1	1	3					
40	8	jar	24	20	30	130	5	0	1	1	5	1	7			
41	1	jar	17	10	15	140	5	0	1	1	3					
41	1	jar	24	12	30	145	5	0	1	1	3					
42	1	jar	16	13	40	120	5	0	1	1	3	7				
43	1	jar	21	13	10	150	5	0	1	1	4					
43	3	jar	22	18	30	110	5	0	1	1	5	7				

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
43	4	jar	28	22	30	140	5	0	1	1	1					
46	0	jar	19	13	25	140	5	0	1	1	5					
48	1	jar	26	16	20	145	5	0	1	1	5					
48	5	jar	19	8	20	30	5	0	1	1	5					
TC	9	jar	19	9	10	160	5	0	1	1	1					
TC	2	jar	19	7	20	140	5	0	1	1	2					
TC		jar	18	14	20	30	5	0	1	1	5					
43	3	jar	27	15	20	145	5	0	1	1	5					
36	2	jar	23	17	20	150	5	0	1	1	1					
48	2	jar	23	12	20	145	5	0	1	1	5	7				
42	4.5	jar	16	8	25	145	5	0	1	1	4					
41	3	jar	19	11	20	145	5	0	1	1	5					
42	1	jar	21	16	30	140	5	1	0	0						
43	9	jar	22	16	20	145	5	1	0	0						
36	1	jar	23	11	30	130	5	1	0	0						
45	1	jar	21	15	20	140	5	1	0	0						
48	2	jar	20	14	15	150	5	1	0	0						
49	1	jar	21	8	20	150	5	1	0	0						
32	2	jar	15	7	30	135	5	1	1	1	4					
45	0	jar	20	8	20	140	5	1	1	1	5					
48	1	jar	19	11	20	140	5	1	1	1	5					
TC	31	jar	14	7	10	155	5	1	1	1	5					
43	3	jar	18	8	10	150	5	1	1	1	5					
43	3	jar	22	16	10	145	5	1	1	1	5	2	7			
48	2	jar	17	8	25	135	5	1	1	1	5	2				
42	6	jar	22	18	30	130	5	1	1	1	2					
42	5	jar	25	15	20	140	5	1	1	1	5					
41	5.5	jar	30	20	35	130	5	2	1	1	5					
4	8	olla	27	23	50	150	1	1	0	1	3					
4	8	olla	19	16	40	150	1	1	0	1	3					
5	2	olla	31	26	5	175	1	1	0	0						
41	2	olla	31	25	40	135	1	1	0	0						
4	8	olla	26	21	60	140	1	2	0	1	3					
4	8	olla	22	17	50	150	1	2	0	1	3					
6	3	olla	50	46	40	165	1	2	0	1	3					
6	3	olla	26	20	40	160	1	2	0	1	3					
45	2_E2	olla	54	48	100	20	1	2	0	1	2					
1	1	olla	39	33	100	20	2	1	0	0						
3	11	olla	42	32	30	130	2	1	0	0						
3	11	olla	21	17	15	175	2	1	0	0						
5	2	olla	23	19	20	170	2	1	0	0						
6	2	olla	31	26	50	160	2	1	0	0						
6	6	olla	40	35	110	20	2	1	0	0						
6	6	olla	34	29	110	20	2	1	0	0						
7	2	olla	17	14	5	130	2	1	0	0						
35	2	olla	36	30	100	80	2	1	0	0						
36	1	olla	31	25	30	130	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	30	26	10	30	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	31	24	30	150	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	40	33	30	20	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	33	26	80	30	2	1	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	31	26	30	140	2	1	0	1	3					
40	7	olla	28	23	100	20	2	1	0	0						
41	1	olla	30	24	20	130	2	1	0	0						
41	3	olla	66	60	30	115	2	1	0	0						
41	4	olla	25	18	30	110	2	1	0	0						
41	4	olla	30	27	40	120	2	1	0	1	3					
41	4	olla	25	20	40	130	2	1	0	1	3					

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
41	4	olla	25	20	35	120	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	32	29	30	120	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	23	18	20	20	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	30	26	40	105	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	48	39	25	130	2	1	0	0						
42	1	olla	41	36	20	20	2	1	0	0						
42	1	olla	38	29	95	40	2	1	0	0						
42	2	olla	51	48	50	20	2	1	0	0						
42	3.5	olla	38	32	65	30	2	1	0	0						
42	3.5	olla	32	27	20	145	2	1	0	0						
42	3.5	olla	38	34	25	145	2	1	0	0						
43	1	olla	31	25	20	140	2	1	0	0						
43	2	olla	30	26	40	130	2	1	0	0						
43	2	olla	36	30	40	120	2	1	0	0						
43	2	olla	37	34	30	130	2	1	0	0						
43	2	olla	34	29	50	110	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	29	22	30	140	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	42	37	85	20	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	38	31	110	20	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	37	30	100	20	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	29	23	40	130	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	25	20	30	140	2	1	0	0						
43	4	olla	30	26	10	10	2	1	0	0						
43	4	olla	40	34	20	130	2	1	0	0						
43	4	olla	31	26	20	150	2	1	0	1	3					
44	3.50E+01	olla	34	27	50	100	2	1	0	0						
45	1	olla	39	33	30	130	2	1	0	0						
45	1	olla	37	33	30	145	2	1	0	0						
47	4	olla	27	22	40	130	2	1	0	0						
48	1	olla	27	22	40	130	2	1	0	0						
TC	28	olla	42	38	30	140	2	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	27	22	20	20	2	1	0	1	3					
43	3	olla	26	20	30	100	2	1	0	0						
36	2	olla	28	25	10	160	2	1	0	0						
43	6	olla	30	24	40	120	2	1	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	30	21	40	120	2	1	0	1	3					
42	6	olla	28	19	40	115	2	1	0	0						
49	3	olla	26	22	40	145	2	1	0	0						
49	3	olla	28	22	15	15	2	1	0	0						
49	3	olla	34	29	30	130	2	1	0	0						
46	5	olla	35	30	30	135	2	1	0	0						
8	1	olla	42	37	40	30	2	1	1	0						
3	7.5	olla	35	31	20	150	2	2	0	1	3					
3	11	olla	32	28	30	140	2	2	0	0						
3	11	olla	34	29	10	170	2	2	0	0						
4	8	olla	29	23	50	150	2	2	0	1	3					
4	8	olla	27	21	60	150	2	2	0	1	3					
6	0	olla	40	32	30	130	2	2	0	0						
46	6	olla	34	27	35	130	2	2	0	0						
7	1	olla	36	27	30	140	2	2	0	0						
34	4	olla	24	20	30	140	2	2	0	1	3					
47	8	olla	27	22	20	150	2	2	0	0						
36	1.5	olla	24	20	70	150	2	2	0	0						
39	3M1	olla	43	36	70	40	2	2	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	37	28	30	130	2	2	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	37	31	30	150	2	2	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	34	29	30	30	2	2	0	0						
40	3.5	olla	40	34	30	120	2	2	0	0						

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
40	3.5	olla	33	27	95	20	2	2	0	0						
40	5(90)	olla	45	42	30	135	2	2	0	0						
41	0	olla	53	44	30	130	2	2	0	0						
41	0	olla	42	35	30	130	2	2	0	0						
41	3.5	olla	38	32	40	30	2	2	0	0						
41	3.5	olla	30	23	20	120	2	2	0	0						
41	4	olla	34	27	30	125	2	2	0	0						
41	5	olla	38	30	25	150	2	2	0	1	3					
41	5.5	olla	32	26	20	30	2	2	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	34	28	40	125	2	2	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	33	27	20	30	2	2	0	0						
41	7	olla	44	38	20	30	2	2	0	0						
42	1	olla	41	32	30	130	2	2	0	1	3					
42	3	olla	45	38	40	120	2	2	0	0						
42	3	olla	36	28	50	130	2	2	0	0						
42	3	olla	30	25	30	20	2	2	0	0						
43	1	olla	32	26	20	30	2	2	0	0						
43	1	olla	30	25	30	130	2	2	0	0						
43	3	olla	31	25	30	125	2	2	0	0						
43	3	olla	49	43	20	30	2	2	0	0						
43	3	olla	31	25	110	20	2	2	0	0						
43	4	olla	32	26	20	150	2	2	0	0						
46	0	olla	36	28	30	135	2	2	0	0						
46	0	olla	35	28	20	130	2	2	0	0						
48	1	olla	52	46	30	150	2	2	0	0						
48	1	olla	41	34	30	120	2	2	0	0						
48	1	olla	40	34	30	140	2	2	0	0						
TC	20	olla	38	26	40	130	2	2	0	0						
TC	36	olla	24	17	20	145	2	2	0	0						
43	3	olla	35	30	85	30	2	2	0	0						
39	3_M1	olla	33	30	30	20	2	2	0	0						
6	1	olla	20	18	20	150	2	2	0	0						
45	2	olla	47	40	40	110	2	2	0	0						
45	2	olla	33	24	35	125	2	2	0	0						
43	6	olla	33	27	40	110	2	2	0	0						
42	4.5	olla	34	27	30	115	2	2	0	0						
48	2	olla	34	22	40	125	2	2	0	0						
48	2	olla	44	38	35	120	2	2	0	0						
42	3.5	olla	39	30	30	120	2	2	0	0						
42	3.5	olla	39	33	20	140	2	2	0	0						
44	1	olla	24	14	30	110	2	2	0	0						
42	6	olla	50	44	30	120	2	2	0	0						
41	5	olla	36	31	20	125	2	2	0	0						
45	2_E1	olla	34	30	30	115	2	2	0	0						
45	2_E2	olla	30	24	20	120	2	2	0	0						
45	2_E2	olla	38	31	40	110	2	2	0	0						
40	1	olla	27	19	35	145	2	2	0	0						
42	5	olla	43	36	25	150	2	2	0	1	3					
42	5	olla	36	30	20	150	2	2	0	0						
42	5	olla	30	24	40	140	2	2	0	1	3					
42	5	olla	33	26	20	150	2	2	0	0						
41	5	olla	34	28	40	120	2	2	0	0						
46	0	olla	35	29	95	20	2	2	0	0						
46	0	olla	31	26	25	125	2	2	0	0						
48	3	olla	30	25	10	170	2	2	0	0						
49	3	olla	39	32	15	15	2	2	0	0						
49	1	olla	34	29	95	25	2	2	0	0						
49	1	olla	36	30	20	140	2	2	0	0						

Transect	Point	FORM	OD	ID	IA	OA	PC	PI	PO	S	SC	D1	D2	D3	D4	DEC
49	2	olla	33	29	20	140	2	2	0	0						
49	2	olla	40	32	30	135	2	2	0	0						
43	5	olla	46	40	20	150	2	2	0	0						
47	5	olla	26	20	30	135	2	2	0	0						
46	5	olla	30	23	30	125	2	2	0	0						
46	5	olla	35	28	25	130	2	2	0	0						
46	5	olla	36	28	100	140	2	2	0	0						
46	4	olla	36	33	70	95	2	2	0	0						
46	4	olla	40	32	30	105	2	2	0	0						
41	5.5	olla	35	28	20	150	2	2	0	0						
49	3	olla	33	27	30	140	2	2	0	0						
49	3	olla	32	25	30	120	2	2	0	0						
49	3	olla	50	44	40	140	2	2	0	0						
49	2	olla	26	21	20	140	2	2	0	0						
49	2	olla	36	30	120	170	2	2	0	0						
43	8	olla	24	19	40	130	2	2	0	0						
48	9.5	olla	44	40	30	145	2	2	0	0						
48	3	olla	44	32	40	170	2	2	0	1	3					
48	3	olla	22	17	20	115	2	2	0	0						
41	3.5	olla	27	20	40	120	3	0	1	1	4					
3	11	olla	24	21	20	175	3	1	0	0						
30	2	olla	35	29	50	120	3	1	0	0						
37	2	olla	32	25	100	10	3	1	0	1	3					
42	7	olla	24	18	30	130	3	1	0	0						
43	3	olla	24	16	30	125	3	1	0	0						
48	11	olla	26	21	40	120	3	1	0	0						
3	11	olla	42	34	30	160	3	2	0	0						
3	11	olla	30	23	40	160	3	2	0	0						
3	11	olla	29	21	40	160	3	2	0	0						
3	11	olla	27	23	40	160	3	2	0	0						
36	1	olla	29	26	20	110	3	2	0	0						
41	4	olla	32	27	40	130	3	2	0	0						
43	3	olla	42	32	40	150	3	2	0	0						
36	1	olla	34	28	30	110	3	2	0	0						
48	1	olla	33	27	40	130	3	2	0	1	4					
41	5.5	olla	29	23	40	130	3	2	0	1	4					
42	6	olla	25	18	30	100	3	2	0	1	4					
42	6	olla	44	40	35	130	3	2	0	0						
45	2_E1	olla	37	30	30	115	3	2	0	1	3					
45	2_E1	olla	38	33	20	150	3	2	0	0						
46	0	olla	30	25	25	145	3	2	0	0						
45	3	olla	32	25	60	110	3	2	0	0						
49	2	olla	23	17	30	120	3	2	0	0						
49	2	olla	34	26	35	105	3	2	0	0						
6	4	olla	45	37	110	20	3	2	1	1	3					
48	2	olla	24	17	25	145	4	1	0	0						
38	4	olla	30	26	25	135	5	1	1	1	5					

Key For Agua Blanca Rim Analysis 2004

Form Codes

- o** olla (1)
- j** jarra (2)
- b** botella (3)
- cue** cuenco (4)
- cm** comal (5)
- cp** compotera (6)
- cz** cazuela (7)
- cant** cantarilla (8)

Type Collection (TC)

10

Inner Rim Diameter (ID)

Outer Rim Diameter (OD)

Inner Rim Angle (IA)

Outer Rim Angle (OA)

Paste Color (PC)

- 5** Light Grey
- 4** Light Brown (Cream)
- 3** Red
- 2** Dark Brown
- 1** Dark Grey (Black)

Paste Inclusions (PI)

- 0** None Visible
- 1** Sand-Sized
- 2** Small Pebbles

Decoration (Dec)

- 0** None
- 1** Excised
- 2** Incised
- 3** Applique

Polish (Po)

- 0** No
- 1** Yes

Slip (S)

- 0** No
- 1** Yes

Slip Color (SC)

- 5** Light Grey
- 4** Light Brown (Cream)
- 3** Red
- 2** Dark Brown
- 1** Dark Grey (Black)

Designs (D)

- 0** None
- 1** Solid
- 2** Wide Lines
- 3** Thin Lines
- 4** Circles
- 5** Circular Spirals
- 6** Square Spirals
- 7** Hatch Marks
- 8** Triangular Spirals
- 9** Figure
Ray
- 11** Triangles

REFERENCES CITED

- Alvarez, Silvia
1999 *De Huancavilcas a Comuneros*. Ediciones Abya-Yala, Quito.
- Arnold, Dean
2000 Does the Standardization of Ceramic Pastes Really Mean Specialization? *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 7(4):333-375.
- Barth, Fredrik
1969 Introduction. In *Ethnic Groups and Boundaries: The Social Organization of Culture Difference*, edited by F. Barth, pp. 9-38. Scandinavian University Books, Oslo.
- Baxter, Michael
1994 *Exploratory Multivariate Analysis in Archaeology*. Edinburgh University Press.
2003 *Statistics in Archaeology*. Arnold, London.
- Bentley, G. Carter
1987 Ethnicity and practice. *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 29:24-55.
- Benzoni, Giralomo
1967 [1956] *La Historia del Nuevo Mundo (Relatos de su viaje por el Ecuador 1547-1550)*. Academia Nacional de Historia, Caracas.
- Binford, Lewis
1962 Archaeology as Anthropology. *American Antiquity* 28(2):217-225.
- Blackman, M. J., Stein, G., and P. Vandiver
1993 The Standardization Hypothesis and Ceramic Mass Production: Technological, Compositional, and Metric Indexes of Craft Specialization at Tell Leilan, Syria. *American Antiquity* 58(1):60-80.
- Bourdieu, Pierre
1977 *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Brumfiel, Elizabeth
1989 Factional Competition in Complex Society. In *Domination and Resistance*, edited by D. Miller, M. Rowlands, and C. Tilley, pp. 127-139. Unwin Hyman, London.
- Bushnell, G. H. S.
1951 *The archaeology of the Santa Elena Peninsula in southwest Ecuador*. Cambridge University Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology, Occasional Publications, no. 1. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.

- Cieza de León, Pedro
1973 [1553] *La Cronica del Peru*. Biblioteca Peruana, Lima.
- Conkey, Margaret
1990 Experimenting with Style in Archaeology: Some Historical and Theoretical Issues. In *The Uses of Style in Archaeology*, edited by M. Conkey and C. Hastorf, pp. 5-17. Cambridge University Press.
- Costin, Cathy Lynn
1991 Craft Specialization: Issues in Defining, Documenting, and Explaining the Organization of Production. *Archaeological Method and Theory* 3:1-56.
- Currie, Elizabeth
1995 Archaeology, ethnohistory and exchange along the coast of Ecuador. *Antiquity* 69:511-26.

2001 Manteño Ceremony and Symbolism: Mortuary Practices and Ritual Activities at López Viejo, Manabí, Ecuador. In *Mortuary Practices and Ritual Associations: Shamanic Elements in Prehistoric Funerary Contexts in South America*, edited by J. Staller and E. Currie, pp. 67-91. BAR International Series 982.
- Dietler, M. and I. Herbich
1998 *Habitus*, Techniques, Style: An Integrated Approach to the Social Understanding of Material Culture and Boundaries. In *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*, edited by M. Stark, pp.232-263. Smithsonian Institute Press, Washington D.C.
- Earle, Timothy
1990 Style and Iconography as Legitimation in Complex Chiefdoms. In *The Uses of Style in Archaeology*, edited by M. Conkey and C. Hastorf, pp. 73-81. Cambridge University Press.
- Estrada, Emilio
1957a *Los Huancavilcas: Ultimas civilizaciones prehistoricas de las costa de Guayas*. Publicacion del Museo Victor Emilio Estrada, No. 3, Guayaquil.

1957b *Prehistoria de Manabí*. Publicacion del Museo Victor Emilio Estrada, No. 4, Guayaquil.

1962 *Arqueologia de Manabí Central*. Publicacion del Museo Victor Emilio Estrada, No. 7, Guayaquil.
- Estrada, Jenny
1988 *La Balsa en la Historia de la Navegación Ecuatoriana*. Instituto de Historia Maritima, Guayaquil.

Hegmon, Michelle

1992 Archaeological Research on Style. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21:517-36.

1998 Technology, Style, and Social Practices: Archaeological Approaches. In *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*, edited by M. Stark, pp. 264-279. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington D.C.

Holm, Olaf

1982 *Cultura Manteña-Huancavilca*. Publicación del Museo Victor Emilio Estrada, No. 3, Guayaquil.

Hosler, Dorothy

1988 Ancient West Mexican Metallurgy: South and Central American Origins and West Mexican Transformations. *American Anthropologist* 90(4):832-855.

Hosler, D., H. Lechtman, and O. Holm

1990 *Axe-Monies and their Relatives*. Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collections, Washington, D.C.

Jijón y Caamaño, Jacinto

1941 *El Ecuador Interandino y Occidental antes de la Conquista Castellana*, Vol. II. Editorial Ecuatoriana, Quito.

Jones, Siân

1997 *The Archaeology of Ethnicity: Constructing Identities in the Past and Present*. Routledge.

Kubler, George

1970 Period, Style and Meaning in Ancient American Art. *New Literary History* 1(2):127-144.

Marcos, Jorge G.

- 1977/78 Cruising to Acapulco and Back with the Thorny Oyster Set: A Model for a Lineal Exchange System. *Journal of the Steward Anthropological Society* 9(1/2):99-132.
- 1981 Informe sobre el Area Ceremonial del Complejo Manteño Huancavilca de la Loma de los Cangrejitos, Valle de Chanduy, Ecuador (OGSECH 4). *El Arquitecto* 1(5):54-65.
- 1995 El mullo y el pututo: la articulación de la ideología y el tráfico a larga distancia en la formación del estado Huancavilca. In *Primer Encuentro de Investigadores de la Costa Ecuatoriana en Europa*, edited by A. Alvarez, S. Alvarez, C. Fauria, and J. Marcos, pp. 97-142. Ediciones Abya-Yala, Quito.
- 2002 Mullo y Pututo para el Gran Caimán: Un Modelo para el Intercambio entre Mesoamérica y Andino América. *Gaceta Arqueológica Andina* 26:13-36.

Masucci, Maria

- 1998 Imported vessels, population movement, or technological change? Tracing the expansion of the prehispanic Manteño, coastal Ecuador. Paper presented at the 97th Annual Meeting of the American Anthropological Association, Philadelphia.

McEwan, Colin

- 2003 'And the Sun Sits in His Seat': Creating Social Order in Andean Culture. Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Illinois, Urbana.

Meggors, Betty

- 1966 *Ecuador*. Praeger, New York.

Mester, Ann

- 1990 *The Pearl Divers of Los Frailes: Archaeological and Ethnohistorical Explorations of Sumptuary Good Trade and Cosmology in the North and Central Andes*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Illinois, Urbana.

Munsell Color

- 1975 *Munsell Soil Color Charts*. Macbeth, Baltimore, Maryland.

Norton, Preseley

- 1986 El señor de Salangone y la liga de mercaderes. *Miscelanea Antropológica Ecuatoriana (Arqueología y Etnohistoria del Sur de Colombia y Norte de Ecuador)* 6:131-144.

Olson, Jan Marie

- 2001 Unequal Consumption: A Study of Domestic Wealth Differentials in Three Late Postclassic Mexican Communities. Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Anthropology, State University of New York, Albany.

Paulsen, Allison

- 1970 *A Chronology of Guangala and Libertad Ceramics of the Santa Elena Peninsula in South Coastal Ecuador*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Department of Anthropology, Columbia University, New York.

- 1974 The Thorny Oyster and the Voice of God: *Spondylus* and *Strombus* in Andean Prehistory. *American Antiquity* 39(4):597-607.

Peregrine, Peter

- 1991 Some Political Aspects of Craft Specialization. *World Archaeology* 23(1):1-11.

Plog, Stephen

- 1983 Analysis of Style in Artifacts. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 12:125-42.

- 1990 Sociopolitical Implications of Stylistic Variation in the American Southwest. In *The Uses of Style in Archaeology*, edited by M. Conkey and C. Hastorf, pp. 61-72. Cambridge University Press.

Pollock, Susan

- 1983 Style and Information: An Analysis of Susiana Ceramics. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 2:354-390.

Rice, Patricia

- 1981 Evolution of specialized pottery production: A trial model. *Current Anthropology* 22:219-240.

- 1991 Specialization, Standardization and Diversity: A Retrospective. In *The Legacy of Anna O. Shepard*, edited by R. Bishop and F. Lange, pp. 257-279. University Press of Colorado, Boulder.

Rowe, Sarah

- 2003 Symbolic Function and Social Design: Analysis of Guangala Polychrome Ceramics from Coastal Ecuador. Unpublished B.A. thesis, Department of Anthropology, Drew University, Madison, New Jersey.

Sackett, James

- 1977 The Meaning of Style in Archaeology: A General Model. *American Antiquity* 42(3):369-380.
- 1985 Style and Ethnicity in the Kalahari: A Reply to Wiessner. *American Antiquity* 50(1):154-159.
- 1990 Style and Ethnicity in Archaeology: The Case for Isochrestism. In *The Uses of Style in Archaeology*, edited by M. Conkey and C. Hastorf, pp. 32-43. Cambridge University Press.

Salomon, Frank

- 1977/78 Pochteca and Mindala: A Comparison of Long-Distance Traders in Ecuador and Mesoameria. *Journal of the Steward Anthropological Society* 9(1/2):231-48.
- 1986 *Native Lords of Quito in the Age of the Incas: the political economy of north Andean chiefdoms*. Cambridge University Press.
- 1987 A North Andean Status Trader Complex under Inka Rule. *Ethnohistory* 34(1):63-77.

Sánchez, Amelia, Yann Graber, Stefan Bohórquez, and Fernando Mejía

- 2003 *Programa de Investigación Arqueológica Japoto: Informe Final de la temporada 2002*. Archaeological report on file at the Instituto Nacional de Patrimonio Cultural, Guayaquil.

Shennan, Stephen

- 1989 Introduction: Archaeological Approaches to Cultural Identity. In *Archaeological Approaches to Cultural Identity*, edited by S. Shennan, pp. 1-32. Unwin Hyman, London.
- 1997 *Quantifying Archaeology*. University of Iowa Press, Iowa City.

Silva, Maria-Isabel

- 1984 Pescadores y Agricultores de la Costa Central de Ecuador: un Modelo Socio-Economico de Asentamientos. Unpublished MA thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Illinois, Urbana.

Smith, A.

- 1986 *The Ethnic Origins of Nations*. Basil Blackwell, Oxford.

Smith, Cameron

- 1999 *Manteño Expedition: 1998-1999. Preliminary Report*. Submitted to Expedition Advisory Center, Royal Geographical Society, London. Copies available from <http://www.sfu.ca/~cmith/genstuff/manteno/report99/report.html>.

- Stark, Miriam
 1998 Technical Choices and Social Boundaries in Material Culture Patterning: An Introduction. In *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*, edited by M. Stark, pp.1-11. Smithsonian Institute Press, Washington D.C.
- Stone, Tammy
 2003 Social Identity and Ethnic Interaction in the Western Pueblos of the American Southwest. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 10(1):31-67.
- Stothert, Karen
 2001 Manteño. In *Middle America*, edited by Peter N. Peregrine and Melvin Ember, pp. 303-327. Encyclopedia of Prehistory, vol. 5, Plenum Press, New York.
- Stothert, Karen and Iván Cruz Cevallos
 2001 Making Spiritual Contact: Snuff Tubes and Other Mortuary Objects from Coastal Ecuador. In *Mortuary Practices and Ritual Associations: Shamanic Elements in Prehistoric Funerary Contexts in South America*, edited by J. Staller and E. Currie, pp. 51-65. BAR International Series 982.
- Tabachnick, B. and L. Fidell
 1983 *Using Multivariate Statistics*. Harper and Row, New York.
- Trigger, Bruce
 1989 *A History of Archaeological Thought*. Cambridge University Press.
- Volland, Martin
 1995 Los Punáes: Una jefatura del Periodo Tardío de Integración. *Miscelanea Antropologica Ecuatoriana* 8:15-27.
- West, Robert
 1961 Aboriginal Sea Navigation between Middle and South America. *American Anthropologist* 63:133-135.
- Wiessner, Polly
 1983 Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points. *American Antiquity* 48(2):253-276.
- 1985 Style or Isochrestic Variation? A Reply to Sackett. *American Antiquity* 50(1):160-166.
- 1990 Is there a Unity to Style? In *The Uses of Style in Archaeology*, edited by M. Conkey and C. Hastorf, pp. 105-112. Cambridge University Press.
- Wobst, Martin

1977 Stylistic Behavior and Information Exchange. In *For the Director: Research Essays in Honor of James B. Griffin*, edited by C. Cleland, pp. 317-42. Museum of Anthropology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor.

- Zarate, Agustín de
1965 [1555] *Historia del Descubrimiento y Conquista del Perú*. Universidad de Buenos Aires.
- Zeidler, James
1977/78 Primitive Exchange, Prehistoric Trade, and the Problem of a Mesoamerican-South American Connection. *Journal of the Steward Anthropological Society* 9(1 and 2):7-39.
- Zevallos Menéndez, Carlos
1986 *La Gran Navegación Prehispánica en el Ecuador*. Comisión Permanente para la Defensa del Patrimonio Nacional, Universidad de Guayaquil, Colección Doctor Honoris Causa, Universidad de Guayaquil, no. 2.
- 1995 *Nuestras Raíces Guacavilcas*. Casa de la Cultural Ecuatoriana Benjamin Carrión, Núcleo del Guayas, Guayaquil.